

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Start / Duration	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Deliverable 5.2

Integrated pelagic model developments

Deliverable Contributors:	Name	Organisation	Role / Title
Deliverable Leader	James Clark	PML	WP5 Lead
Contributing Author(s)	Annette Samuelson	NERSC	WP5 Contributor
	Çağlar Yumruktepe	NERSC	WP5 Contributor
	Sarah Albernh	CLS	WP5 Contributor
	Anja Lindenthal	BSH	WP5 Contributor
	Josefine Hahn	BSH	WP5 Contributor
	Mokrane Belharet	MOi	WP5 Contributor
	Rebecca Millington	PML	WP5 Contributor
	Giulia Bonino	CMCC	WP5 Contributor
	Mathurin Choblet	ULiège	WP5 Contributor
	Helen Powley	PML	WP5 Contributor
	Giovanni Galli	OGS	WP5 Contributor
Gianpiero Cossarini	OGS	WP5 Contributor	

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

	Paolo Lazzari	OGS	WP5 Contributor
	Eva Alvarez	OGS	WP5 Contributor
	Loïc Macé	ULiège	WP5 Contributor
	Jozef Skakala	PML	WP5 Contributor
Reviewer(s)	Jeremy Blackford	PML	Internal Reviewer
Final review and approval	Stefano Ciavatta	MOi	Project Coordinator

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Document History:

Release	Date	Reason for Change	Status	Distribution
1.0		Initial document, reviewed	Released	Internal

To cite this document

Clark, J., Samuelson, A., Yumruktepe, Ç., Albernhe, S., Lindenthal, A., Hahn, J., Belharet, M., Millington, R., Bonino, G., Choblet, M., Powley, H., Galli, G., Cossarini, G., Lazzari, P., Alvarez, E., Macé, L., & Skakala, J. (2025). NECCTON Integrated pelagic model developments (D5.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14926411>

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Executive Summary	6
2	Introduction	7
2.1	Scope of the document.....	7
2.2	Structure of the document	8
3	Processes summary	8
4	Mesozooplankton.....	10
4.1	Introduction	10
4.2	Mesozooplankton Diel Vertical Migration	11
4.2.1	Background	11
4.2.2	Theory	11
4.2.3	Implementation.....	12
4.2.4	Testing.....	16
4.3	Mesozooplankton light dependent mortality	19
4.3.1	Background	19
4.3.2	Theory	20
4.3.3	Implementation.....	21
4.3.4	Testing.....	21
5	Micronekton	22
5.1	Introduction	22
5.2	One-way interactions with biogeochemistry	23
5.2.1	Background	23
5.2.2	Theory	24
5.2.3	Implementation.....	25
5.2.4	Testing.....	26
6	Suspended Particulate Matter	28
6.1	Introduction	28
6.2	Suspended Particulate Matter Dynamics	28
6.2.1	Background	28
6.2.2	Theory	30
6.2.3	Implementation.....	38
6.2.4	Testing.....	38
7	Particulate Organic Matter	44
7.1	Introduction	44
7.2	Sinking and remineralisation of particulate organic carbon.....	44
7.2.1	Background	44
7.2.2	Theory	45

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

7.2.3	Implementation	46
7.2.4	Testing	48
8	Dissolved Organic Matter	53
8.1	Introduction	53
8.2	Dissolved Organic Carbon Exudation.....	53
8.2.1	Background	53
8.2.2	Theory	53
8.2.3	Implementation	54
8.2.4	Testing	57
9	Bio-optical modelling.....	61
9.1	Introduction	61
9.2	Reflectance	62
9.2.1	Background	62
9.2.2	Theory	62
9.2.3	Implementation	63
9.2.4	Testing	65
10	Conclusions.....	73
11	References.....	74

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

1 Executive Summary

The NECCTON D5.2 report provides a description of the additions and improvements made to the suite of marine biogeochemical models being used in NECCTON, and their relationship to the new pelagic lower trophic level products that are being delivered. It is intended to serve as a reference for internal and external users of the products, allowing them to understand the processes that influence spatio-temporal patterns within the data, the underlying assumptions and potential sources of error. The document includes a description of each process, and its encapsulation in mathematical form. It also includes a brief description of the implementation in code, and the results of testing the new models.

In total, the work enables the delivery of five new products, and involved developments to all seven of the biogeochemical models that currently support the delivery of the Copernicus Marine Service. Included in this report are:

- A description of new processes designed to improve the way mesozooplankton are represented in models. Mesozooplankton are a key link between the lower and higher trophic levels of the marine food web, and thus an important determinant of fish production. The work in NECCTON has involved adding a new description of Diel Vertical Migration for mesozooplankton, and a parameterisation of light dependent mortality – two factors which are known to be a major source of uncertainty in models. The results show the new models reproduce changes in the vertical positioning of mesozooplankton through the day-night cycle.
- A description of work focussed on resolving feedbacks between micronekton and the lower trophic levels of the marine food web, with the aim of better capturing seasonal changes in micronekton biomass. Micronekton are organisms which measure (2 – 20) cm in size and are an important source of food for higher trophic level organisms. To our knowledge, very few studies have focused on micronekton seasonality, and none have explored it using models. By addressing this gap, we position ourselves as pioneers in advancing the understanding of micronekton seasonal dynamics.
- A description of a new model of Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM). SPM is a collective term for the inorganic (e.g., mineral) and organic (e.g., detritus; see next section) particulates suspended in the water column. It is an indicator of sediment transport, water clarity and quality; and has important implications for pelagic and benthic productivity and erosion. It can also act as a vector for the transfer of pollutants and contaminants. In NECCTON, a new SPM module has been developed for the fine-scale, unstructured hydrodynamic model SHYFEM-MPI. The model was tested in 3D using a local, high-resolution model domain for the Tyrrhenian Sea. This module was then rewritten for FABM and incorporated into the ERSEM model, where it will support the delivery of a new SPM product for the Northwest European Shelf domain. A separate model of SPM was developed for BAMHBI, where it was run with NEMO to study the transport of organic SPM in the Black Sea.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

- The results of improving parameterisations relating to the production and processing of particulate and dissolved organic matter. The work has enabled the delivery of a product representing particulate organic carbon for four domains: the Arctic, the Mediterranean Sea, the Northwest European Shelf and the Baltic Sea. We have improved the underlying models by revisiting how sinking and remineralisation rates are modelled using recent data from the published literature. For dissolved organic carbon, the underlying models were improved by revisiting phytoplankton dissolved organic carbon exudations rates. In test simulations, the developments are shown to better reproduce new observations for both particulate and dissolved organic carbon.
- A description of a new bio-optical model which supports the delivery of a new product for multispectral remote sensing reflectance, which can be directly compared with satellite reflectance data. The accurate simulation of light penetration and reflectance is of fundamental importance in marine ecosystem models, as light is the primary source of energy input to the marine ecosystem. The new bio-optical model can be used to compute seabed irradiance and to study the dynamics of pollutants (e.g. mercury photoreduction).

The document is designed to be read in conjunction with NECCTON D5.1, where the new pelagic lower trophic level products are defined. The document also provides context to the suite of multi-decadal hindcasts which are being run within NECCTON, and which include the new processes described herein.

2 Introduction

2.1 Scope of the document

The objective of the document is to provide a description of the additions and improvements made to the suite of marine biogeochemical models being used in NECCTON, and their relationship to the new pelagic lower trophic level products that are being delivered. It is intended to serve as a reference for internal and external users of the products, allowing them to understand the processes that influence spatio-temporal patterns within the data, the underlying assumptions and potential sources of error.

The document includes a description of each process and the approach to parameterising it within each model. Processes are grouped under the lower trophic level product to which they are most directly related. Where appropriate, theoretical frameworks are introduced with reference to the published literature. Brief mathematical descriptions of each parameterisation are provided. Where the mathematical description is excessively long, the reader is directed to the published literature for more detailed treatments. A summary of the implementation in code and the approach to configuring the model with the new parameterisation is also summarised. References to public repositories where the code is being hosted are provided.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Table 1 Glossary

Acronym	Meaning
Physical Models	
GOTM	General Ocean Turbulence Model
NEMO	Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean
HYCOM	Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model
Coupling Frameworks	
FABM	Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models
Marine ecosystem and biogeochemical models	
ERSEM	European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model
PISCES	Pelagic Interactions Scheme for Carbon and Ecosystem Studies
ERGOM	Ecological ReGional Ocean Model
ECOSMO	ECOSystem Model
BFM	Biogeochemical Flux Model
BAMHBI	Biogeochemical Model for Hypoxic and Benthic Influenced areas
SEAPODYM	Spatial Ecosystem and POPulation Dynamics Model

For each process, a set of tests are described, which are intended to demonstrate both how the parameterisation works, and that it has been implemented correctly. Where appropriate, comparisons are made to observations to demonstrate correct behaviour. A full model validation in 3D based on multiyear or multidecadal hindcast simulations is not provided here, but in D9.1.

The document is designed to be read in conjunction with NECCTON D5.1, where the new pelagic lower trophic level products are defined.

2.2 Structure of the document

The document is structured as follows. Section 3 provides a synthetic list of the processes that have been parameterised and the products to which they relate. Sections 4 - 9 provide a description of each new process, including: i) background theoretical considerations, ii) a description of the implementation in code, and iii) the result of test simulations and associated analyses. A summary is provided at the end of the report. For reference, a glossary of the different models being used is provided in Table 1.

3 Processes summary

The list of processes that have been implemented and parameterised in NECCTON, grouped by the new lower trophic level pelagic products that they support, are given in Table 2.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Table 2 List of processes, grouped by the products that they support. Also listed are the models in which the new processes have been implemented, the URL for the associated code repository, and the domain where the models will be run.

Associated product(s)	Process(es)	Model	Code repository [branch]	Application domain
Mesozooplankton biomass	Diel vertical migration	ECOSMO	https://github.com/nasencenter/ECOSMO	Arctic
	Diel vertical migration	ERSEM	https://github.com/pmlmodelling/ersem-neccton [dvm]	Northwest European Shelf
	Diel vertical migration	PISCES	https://github.com/MoBelharet/fabm-pisces-4.2 https://github.com/MoBelharet/fabm-migration	Global
	Diel vertical migration	ERGOM	https://gitlab.opencode.de/bsh/neccton	Baltic
	Light dependent mortality	ERGOM	https://gitlab.opencode.de/bsh/neccton	Baltic
	Micronekton dynamics	SEAPODYM-LMTL with PISCES	https://github.com/neccton-algo/SEAPODYM-1D-IET	Global
	Suspended particulate matter	SPM dynamics	BFM	https://github.com/giubonino/SPMmodule
SPM dynamics		ERSEM	https://github.com/pmlmodelling/ersem-neccton [spm]	Northwest European Shelf
SPM dynamics		BAMHBI	https://github.com/mchoblet/SPM_wave_resuspension	Black Sea
Particulate Organic Matter	POC sinking and remineralisation	ERSEM	https://github.com/pmlmodelling/ersem-neccton	Northwest European Shelf

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

	POC sinking and remineralisation	BFM (FABM)	https://github.com/inogs/bfmforfabm	Mediterranean
	POC sinking and remineralisation	ERGOM	https://gitlab.opencod.e.de/bsh/neccton	Baltic
	POC sinking and remineralisation	ECOSMO	https://github.com/nanscenter/ECOSMO	Arctic
Dissolved Organic Matter	DOC exudation	ERSEM	https://github.com/pmlmodelling/ersem-neccton	Northwest European Shelf
	DOC exudation	ECOSMO	https://github.com/nanscenter/ECOSMO	Arctic
	DOC exudation	ERGOM	https://gitlab.opencod.e.de/bsh/neccton	Baltic
Reflectance	Bio-optics	BFM (FABM)	https://github.com/inogs/bfmforfabm	Mediterranean
	Bio-optics	ERSEM	https://github.com/pmlmodelling/fabm-spectral [rrs]	Northwest European Shelf
	Bio-optics	ERGOM	https://gitlab.opencod.e.de/bsh/neccton	Baltic
	Bio-optics	BHAMBI	https://github.com/loic-mace/bamhbi-rt	Black Sea

4 Mesozooplankton

4.1 Introduction

Mesozooplankton are heterotrophic organisms in the size range from 0.2 to 20 mm that move with ocean currents but can actively migrate vertically through the water column. Mesozooplankton generally feed on primary producers, microzooplankton and detritus particles. They are an important prey for fish larva and planktivorous fish and therefore represent an important link between primary producers and higher trophic levels in the marine food web. In NECCTON, we have improved the way mesozooplankton are represented in models by including parameterisations of two processes: light-dependent mortality and diel vertical migration (DVM). These developments support the provision of a new mesozooplankton biomass product for five regions:

- The Global Ocean

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

- Iberia-Biscay-Ireland (IBI)
- Baltic
- Arctic
- Northwest Shelf domains.

The mesozooplankton product for the IBI domain stands alone in the sense it will be delivered along with the micronekton product using the SEAPODYM model coupled to PISCES.

In this section, we describe the parameterisations of DVM and light-dependent mortality and their implementation in the different models. A set of 1D simulations are used to test the two parameterisations.

4.2 Mesozooplankton Diel Vertical Migration

4.2.1 Background

Zooplankton are preyed upon by both tactile and visual predators, with visual predators able to find their prey better when there is light. Diel vertical migration (DVM) is believed to help zooplankton to avoid being predated upon. DVM occurs on a daily cycle, with mesozooplankton staying at depth during the daytime to hide from visual predators. They then ascend towards the surface at night to feed ². DVM behaviour is an important component of carbon and nutrient flow within the food web, interacting with both the transfer of materials to the upper trophic levels through grazing, and the export of carbon to the mesopelagic through active sinking ^{1,3}. Despite its importance, DVM is not typically represented in Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) models, where both zooplankton grazing and DVM processes represent significant sources of error ^{4,5}. A parameterisation of DVM was first implemented in the ECOSMO model and tested in the Arctic. As a standalone FABM module, it was subsequently ported to the ERSEM, PISCES and ERGOM models as part of NECCON.

4.2.2 Theory

Light intensity is believed to be a leading factor in determining the position of migrators in the water column, where migrators position themselves within certain isolumes (zones with a preferred level of light for a given organism) at times of available light at the surface ^{2,6}. Light varies with incoming solar radiation, varying cloud cover and even the phases of the moon. In this context, photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), a spatially and temporally varying environmental variable in FABM, was chosen as the primary indicator for the positioning of migrating organisms in the water column. The following are the complete set of environmental conditions (ECs) that the DVM formulation considers when positioning the migrating organisms:

- 1) Instantaneous PAR at the ocean surface
- 2) Average PAR at the surface for the past 24-hour period
- 3) Water column integrated total food concentration for that migrator
- 4) Number of sunlit hours for the past 24-hour period

In the model, the behaviour of migrating organisms is to reside at depths that range from the surface to a deep layer at night, or a band below the surface following certain isolumes at daytime. This represents a simplification, as in the real-world, the relationship between light and depth is

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

much more complex, and not well understood. For example, in the high latitudes, there is no continuous day/night cycle, and events like the polar night (absence of PAR at the surface) or polar day (24-hour light availability) pose challenges to the coding of a generic module.

In its simplest form, we develop a model which relates, at each time-step in a simulation, the ECs to two specific PAR isolumes. These are the *upper* and *lower* PAR levels of the high concentration band of migrators. We assign each model point a “0” or a “1” which indicate a “low” or “high” probability that the migrator will be present, followed by a weight-dependent random distribution of the water column integrated migrator biomass.

Given the complexity of the environmental conditions that affect migratory behaviour, which must be parameterised, the development of the DVM framework was conducted in two parallel paths. In the first, the two isolumes were simply parameterised as a function of surface PAR, which is provided by the model. This approach is called Simple-DVM. In the second approach, machine learning is used with observations of environmental conditions and acoustic backscatter to determine isolume depths. This approach is called ML-DVM. Much of the work on the paramaterisation of the ML-DVM was conducted in NECCON Task 4.3.1.

4.2.3 Implementation

The Simple-DVM and ML-DVM approaches were first developed using the FABM-ECOSMO model setup. The Simple-DVM approach was then ported to the ERSEM, ERGOM and PISCES models, while the ML-DVM approach was developed using FABM ECOSMO. As a standalone FABM module (see <https://github.com/nanscenter/nersc/tree/main/dvm>), the code was easy to port between models. It also works generically so that any model state variable can be activated to migrate at run time using the model configuration file. The migration behaviour is hardcoded to respond to the four environmental conditions specified above.

Simple-DVM

In the Simple-DVM approach, parameters are set for the upper and lower PAR levels. As a result of numerical experiments, these were set to values of 0.5 % and 0.00001 % of surface PAR respectively.

ML-DVM

The ML-DVM approach is much more complex and is a result of training a ML model on environmental conditions observed at mooring stations in the Barents Sea; ATWAIN (81.55N 30.83E

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Start / Duration	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Atwain mooring station acoustic backscatter density anomaly time series for 2021

Figure 1 Normalized acoustic backscatter density anomaly (a) is compared against normalized generic and conservative simulated migrating organism (b) at the ATWAIN mooring station in the Barents Sea (81.55N 30.83E ~800 m depth). Each box depicts an hourly day-night cycle averaged over a week. Shades of grey depict the normalized concentrations. Yellow markers denote the maximum concentration depth for each hour. Red and cyan markers denote normalized concentration = 0.8, depicting the upper and lower depth band high concentration boundaries. The weeks that are crossed out were omitted from the dataset for machine learning experiments as the defining the upper and lower boundaries for these weeks were challenging.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Start / Duration	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

~800 m depth), M1 (79.6N 28.1E ~260 m depth) and M5 (77.1N 35.05E ~150 m depth). The acoustic backscatter density anomaly was used to define the upper and lower depths of the high abundance layer for the organisms. The noise of this dataset was reduced by taking weekly averages for each hour of the day (Figure 1a). The maximum density for that hour is selected and the data for that day was normalized against this maximum. The density that matches 0.8 for that day (both above and below the maximum) were chosen as the depth of the upper and lower boundaries of the high concentration band. Not all profiles could produce definitive upper and lower isolumes; e.g., the depth range of the backscatter data was not sufficient to locate the isolumes close to the surface, or below the maximum. In such cases, at nighttime, the organisms were assumed to cover a range starting at the surface, and for the isolume at depth, the distance from the maximum to the upper boundary was chosen as the distance of the maximum to the lower boundary. In some cases, the 0.8 criteria was unable to define a continuous isolume. If so, that week was omitted in ML experiments (see crossed out weeks in Figure 1b).

We do not have PAR measurements at the mooring stations. Instead of using observations, PAR profiles were simulated using 1D GOTM-FABM-ECOSMO, while restoring to temperature and salinity data from Arctic reanalysis simulations ⁷ for these stations. The simulated PAR and integrated prey concentration were extracted as profile time series. Mean surface net solar radiation (hourly ERA5 “mean_surface_net_short_wave_radiation_flux” data) were downloaded ⁸, multiplied by 0.42 to calculate PAR and were further multiplied by the ice concentration. Average PAR at the surface and the number of sunlit hours for the past 24-hour period were calculated based on the ERA5 data. Shortwave radiation, PAR profiles and food concentrations were also weekly averaged to achieve a day cycle matching the timing of the acoustic backscatter data. These datasets together were used in ML experiments. The datasets cover the years 2020 and 2021.

A decision tree approach was chosen for the ML experiments. The reason behind this choice is to simplify the transfer of the parameters to FABM Fortran code. The number of decision layers were limited to 2 – 4. The ATWAIN station dataset (every other week) was chosen as the training dataset, and the remaining half of the ATWAIN dataset and the entirety of M1 and M5 datasets were chosen as the validation data. We opted for four different cases to build the decision trees to increase the representability of the parameters: (1) polar night (24-hour mean surface par < 10^{-3} W m⁻²), (2) polar summer (number of sunlit hours = 24), (3) day-night cycle dark (PAR < 10^{-3} W m⁻²) and (4) day-night cycle light (PAR >= 10^{-3} W m⁻²). Each case has its own set of if/else conditions. As an output, each decision tree relates the input parameters to PAR values for Cases 2, 3 and 4, and a depth value for Case 1. These values are then used by FABM models to relocate the migrating state variable in the water column.

Fixed point (Barents Sea ATWAIN, M1 and M5 mooring stations and Norwegian Sea 66N –2E) 1D GOTM-FABM-ECOSMO setups were implemented for designing and testing the DVM framework. Figure 1b depicts the simulated generic and conservative (no biological sources and sinks) migrating organism in the Barents Sea ATWAIN mooring timeseries station. Initially, this conservative tracer was used to evaluate the positioning of the organism and its mass conservation. The observed upper (red markers) and lower (cyan markers) boundaries of the high-density layers defined by the maximum density position (yellow markers) was successfully transferred to the 1D GOTM-ECOSMO

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 2 1D results generated using the ECOSMO model showing the impact of DVM. a) Hovmöller diagram at a fixed-point location in the Norwegian Sea (66N -2E), based on a 2-year 1D GOTM-FABM-ECOSMO simulation. b) Simulated total phytoplankton, micro- and mesozooplankton concentrations where DVM is not active (top plots), active (middle plots) and their difference (bottom plots; top - middle).

simulation and different seasonal conditions were generally captured by the model. As such, during polar night (weeks 8 - 18), the migrators were located near the surface throughout the day, and during polar day (weeks 28 - 47) they were mainly located at depth, and in between for the regular day-night cycles, the varying diurnal positions and their timing generally match the observed locations. There are some mismatches, and these mainly occur in weeks where the actual surface light availability at the mooring stations (e.g. during periods where the sun is below the horizon (weeks 1 - 4, 19 - 21), but the sky still has diffuse light), was not simulated by ERA5 reanalysis (Figure not shown). Therefore, the model classifies these periods as polar night situations, and locates the migrator near the surface, whereas in reality, the migrators have already started their diurnal cycles. During weeks 32 - 37, there was a significant shallowing of the observed high-density layer which was not captured by the model. The reasoning of this rise is not clear; however, it is assumed to be a combination of avoiding light, need for prey and an increase in light attenuation due to the phytoplankton bloom. The ML parameters fail to reproduce this unique set of environmental conditions, though for the summer period, the model generally predicts the upper and lower

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

boundaries well. This new parameterization has been tested in ECOSMO, and when finalized, will also be distributed to the ERSEM, ERGOM and PISCES models.

4.2.4 Testing

Here we discuss results from the ECOSMO model using the ML-DVM approach, and the ERSEM, ERGOM and PISCES models using the Simple-DVM approach. All results are based on 1D simulations.

1D HYCOM-ECOSMO simulation in the Norwegian Sea

The testing of the ML-DVM parameterization was conducted at a fixed-point location in the Norwegian Sea (66N –2E; ~2000 m depth) using 1D GOTM-FABM-ECOSMO model with 1-hour ERA5 atmospheric forcing and WOA18 initial conditions. The purpose of this test was to evaluate whether the tuned parameters for the Barents Sea that were validated using a conservative tracer (Figure 1) are applicable to a different part of the pan-Arctic domain using non-conservative realistic migrating organisms, i.e. mesozooplankton. The daily averaged simulated mesozooplankton concentration (Figure 2a) suggests that the DVM parameterization that was tuned with machine learning experiments using the backscatter density anomaly in the Barents Sea can allow mesozooplankton to cover a depth range from the surface to hundreds of meters below the surface. DOC release by phytoplankton is active in these simulations. To achieve realistic concentrations in test runs, the maximum grazing rate was increased, the grazing half saturation constant decreased leading to faster feeding, and mesozooplankton mortality was modified to be light-dependent as described in the next section. The new model parameterisations were tuned to give similar biomass to the original model – this is a common problem in model development as existing parameterisations have often been tuned themselves to cover for missing processes. A final parameter tuning will be performed when the ML-DVM code is finalised. Although resulting biomasses were similar, significant changes in the distribution of plankton biomass are observed (Figure 2b). When DVM was active, phytoplankton biomass was reduced near the surface and increased below the surface. Microzooplankton biomass generally increased. These suggest that the grazing pressure applied by mesozooplankton on phyto- and microzooplankton has changed. Even though mesozooplankton total biomass is similar in both simulations, the biomass is spread across a greater depth range.

1D GOTM-ERGOM simulation in the Baltic Sea

This testing is conducted using a 1D-GOTM-ERGOM-DVM configuration for the Baltic Sea Station BMPJ1, located in the Baltic Proper (57°19,20' N, 20°03.00' E, ~ 220 m depth). The simulation is run for 11 years (2013-2023) with 1-hour ERA5 atmospheric forcing and a spin-up phase of 50 years. The ERGOM model and the DVM module are coupled using FABM to the physical ocean model.

The Baltic Sea exhibits strong vertical stratification, with a permanent halocline located at approximately 60 meters, separating the surface and deeper water layers. Below the halocline, the presence of zooplankton is limited due to low oxygen levels, especially pronounced at depths exceeding 150-200 meters. The ERGOM model, which is restricted to a single zooplankton pool, does not represent species capable of surviving under anoxic conditions. However, the DVM module redistributes zooplankton vertically after the spring bloom throughout the entire water column. At the moment, Simple-DVM code does not restrict migration through the anoxic conditions. ML-DVM

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 3 GOTM-ERGOM simulation from 2013-2023 at the BMPJ1 station in the Baltic Sea. The upper panel shows the zooplankton biomass in the ERGOM-base simulation. The middle panel shows zooplankton biomass with DVM module. The lower panel shows the difference between DVM and base.

code is being tuned to enable avoiding low-oxygen concentrations. We expect with the final version of the code, this issue will be resolved.

Figure 3 compares a base simulation (no diel vertical migration, DVM) with a DVM-enabled simulation to assess differences in zooplankton behaviour and distribution. In the base simulation, zooplankton concentrations are relatively uniform in the surface layers, with periodic increases indicating phytoplankton blooms. The DVM simulation shows a vertical migration pattern, with zooplankton aggregating near the surface and descending to deeper waters.

1D NEMO-PISCES simulation at HOT and KERFIX oceanographic stations

Testing of the DVM model developed by NERSC has been conducted by MOi using 1D NEMO-FABM-PISCES 3-years-simulations that have been configured for the Hawaii Ocean Timeseries (HOT) (22.5°N, 158°W) and the KERFIX (50°S, 68° E) oceanographic stations. In these simulations, we tested a scenario with activated mesozooplankton DVM to compare it with a reference scenario (without DVM), while assuming all mesozooplankton undertake DVM. The impact of DVM on mesozooplankton concentration has been investigated throughout the water column between 0 and 1000 m depth. Coherently with the project work plan, the results of the simulations presented here are still preliminary because the model parameters need to be tuned when DVM is active. The tuning of BGC

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

model parameters will take place after the DVM behaviour is fine-tuned against acoustics data in the Barents Sea.

Figure 4 Comparison of mesozooplankton vertical distributions (0-1000 m) between two scenarios (Reference and DVM) during 3-year simulations at HOT and KERFIX oceanographic stations. The upper and middle panels show the results obtained under the reference simulations (without DVM) and DVM simulations (active mesozooplankton DVM), respectively. The lower panel shows the difference between the two scenarios (DVM - reference).

The results of these comparisons are illustrated in Figure 4. In the reference simulations (upper panel), mesozooplankton are mainly concentrated in the epipelagic zone (0-200m depth), with a slightly deeper distribution at HOT than KERFIX. At both stations, when DVM is activated (Middle panel), mesozooplankton are no longer concentrated at the surface layer but descend up to 400-500 m depth. This lower limit of DVM shows a seasonal variability that is mainly dependent on light penetration in the water column, which in turn is related to the chlorophyll concentration (not shown). The difference between the two scenarios over time and depth (lower panel) shows negative values in the epipelagic zone (0 - 200 m) and positive ones between 200 and 400-500 m depth. This is due to the vertical movement of mesozooplankton during the daytime from the surface to the deep waters.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 5 DVM-ERSEM-1D: Depth-averaged mesozooplankton biomass (mg C m^{-3}) at L4. Model output from GOTM-ERSEM baseline and with DVM in blue and orange lines respectively. Grey points show observations of mesozooplankton biomass from the Western Channel Observatory.

GOTM-ERSEM simulation at Station L4 and the North Sea

DVM was tested in ERSEM first in 1D using GOTM at L4, a coastal station with depth 50m. Figure 5 shows depth-averaged mesozooplankton biomass from original GOTM-ERSEM and with DVM. When DVM was included, the feeding rate of mesozooplankton was increased, otherwise, the parameter set was unchanged from the baseline run. The model output was compared to observations of mesozooplankton biomass from the Western Channel Observatory⁹. The model results with DVM were comparable to without DVM and both similarly followed the trends in the observed data, e.g. peaking in summer with around 30 mg C m^{-3} .

DVM was then tested in ERSEM in 3D in the North Sea using the hydrodynamic model PyGETM. PyGETM-ERSEM was run unmodified and including DVM, from 2006 to 2010 inclusive. The depth integrated biomass of mesozooplankton averaged over the years 2008-2010 inclusive can be seen in Figure 6. In general, the magnitude of biomass was similar when model output with DVM was compared to the baseline; however there was a small increase in biomass in the northern North Sea and a decrease in the southern North Sea.

4.3 Mesozooplankton light dependent mortality

4.3.1 Background

Simple marine ecosystem models use constant mortality to control the biomass and number of zooplankton. In these models such as ERGOM, mesozooplankton (hereafter zooplankton) is the highest order species in the food web. Its biomass is controlled by grazing g and respiration l rates, as well as a mortality rate μ . A constant mortality does not realistically simulate real oceanic conditions where visual predators feed on zooplankton¹⁰. Zooplankton mortality involves both death due to ageing and disease, and predation by fish¹¹. To improve biogeochemical model coupling to biomass species of higher orders, zooplankton mortality is a key process. The choice of the mortality parameterisation is difficult since basic factors are poorly known. A seasonal variation in mortality has been used previously¹².

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 6 DVM-ERSEM-3D: Mesozooplankton biomass in mg C m⁻² from pygetm-ERSEM depth-integrated and averaged over 2008-2010 inclusive. Subplots show output from (a) baseline, (b) with DVM, (c) with DVM minus baseline.

A light-dependent mortality of zooplankton considers both a daily and a seasonal cycle in zooplankton predation. The parameterisation of light-dependent mortality was added to the ERGOM model and not tested in any other models.

4.3.2 Theory

In the model environment of GOTM-ERGOM, there is one zooplankton tracer, which feeds on large and small phytoplankton, and blue-green algae. We do not consider stage-dependent mortality as did Neumann and Kremp (2005). Hence, we only have one mortality rate as a sink for zooplankton biomass. We have a reference run (base) with constant mortality $\mu_c = 0.03 \text{ day}^{-1}$. Furthermore, we run the GOTM-FABM-ERGOM model system with light-dependent mortality μ (zoo_mort_light = zml). μ is given by:

$$\mu(z) = \mu_0 + \mu_I(z) \quad (1)$$

where μ_0 is a constant and

$$\mu_I(z) = C \times \frac{I(z)}{I_h + I(z)} \quad (2)$$

with C as the maximum mortality due to predation by visual predators and $I(z)$ the depth-dependent available light and I_h the half-saturation constant. The values for two cases which have been considered in Neumann and Kremp (2005) can be found in Table 3.

Zooplankton mortality is applied in ERGOM as follows:

$$Zoo(z, t) = Zoo(z, t - 1) - Zoo_{eff}(z, t - 1) \times \mu(z) \quad (3)$$

where $Zoo_{eff} = \frac{Zoo^2}{Zoo_{close}}$ is the effective zooplankton concentration (mol kg⁻¹) assumed for mortality and respiration. It includes a closure term, which assures that zooplankton do not go extinct. With $Zoo_{close} = 0.09 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$ the closure parameter of zooplankton.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Table 3 Parameters for light-dependent mortality for two cases after Neumann and Kremp (2005).

	μ_0 [1/day]	C [1/day]	I_h
Case1	0.005	0.035	0.001
Case2	0.015	0.015	0.001

In ERGOM, Zooplankton has phytoplankton grazing as sources and mortality and respiration as sinks. Grazing and respiration remain unchanged.

4.3.3 Implementation

The GOTM-FABM-ERGOM modelling system consists of the 1D physical ocean model GOTM coupled using FABM to the biogeochemical model ERGOM. The model uses a configuration for the BMPJ1 Station north of Bornholm Island in the Baltic Sea. Its location is 57.13 °N and 19.78 °E and it has a depth of 220m. PAR comes from the GOTM light routine and is used for calculating the light-dependent mortality.

Light-dependent mortality was integrated as a depth-dependent function into the mortality process of zooplankton. This is directly added in the ERGOM code, using its code generation toolbox.

The variable $I(z)$, comes from the host model (i.e. GOTM) and is equivalent to PAR.

4.3.4 Testing

An 11-year 1D GOTM-FABM-ERGOM simulation was used to investigate the effects of light-dependent mortality on zooplankton biomass. The reference setup, ERGOM-base, is compared to the light-dependent mortality setup (ERGOM-zml), which was run for the two distinct cases as outlined in Table 3. The output consists of daily values, averaged over multiple years to illustrate the seasonal cycle of zooplankton biomass.

The two cases shown in Figure 7 are compared to the baseline simulation. They display differences in seasonal patterns. Changes in light-dependent mortality lead to slightly higher zooplankton mortality, which increases detritus production. In this version of the ERGOM model, zooplankton is represented in a simplified way, without different life stages. This simplification results in higher overall zooplankton concentrations in Case 1 and Case 2 compared to the baseline. As a result, phytoplankton experiences more grazing pressure, especially during periods of high bloom activity. Additionally, the light field in deeper water decreases due to phytoplankton self-shading, but this effect is reduced when zooplankton activity increases.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 7 Multi-year mean climatological zooplankton annual cycle at BMPJ1, depth-integrated for four thicknesses and averaged daily. Displayed for the Baseline (red), Case 1 (blue), and Case 2 (green) simulations.

5 Micronekton

5.1 Introduction

Micronekton refers to marine organisms ranging in size from 2 to 20 cm, encompassing various taxa such as crustaceans, fish, and cephalopods with the ability to swim. These organisms occupy an intermediate position in the oceanic trophic web, feeding on zooplankton and serving as a primary food source for larger marine predators. They play a crucial role in the biological pump by exporting and sequestering carbon to the deep ocean, facilitated by their diurnal vertical migration (DVM) - like mesozooplankton, micronekton migrate daily between the surface, where they feed at night, and the deep ocean, where they evade predators during the day.

Recent estimates suggest that fish, including those classes as micronekton, performing DVM contribute approximately 20 % (9-29%) of global carbon export and 32 % (18-43%) of oceanic carbon sequestration¹³. However, large discrepancies exist in quantifying these carbon fluxes, with the contribution of micronekton and the mesopelagic migrant pump's to deep-ocean carbon export

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

estimated between 15 % and 50 %^{14–17}. These discrepancies partly arise from variations in micronekton biomass estimates, which range from 1 Gt to 10 Gt (Irigoyen et al., 2014; St John et al., 2016; Anderson et al., 2019; Proud et al., 2019).

To enhance the representation of biogeochemical processes, ecosystem models have been coupled with biogeochemical models^{18,19}. The Spatial Ecosystem and Population Dynamics Model (SEAPODYM), offers a different perspective, focusing on energy transfer within a simplified global marine ecosystem comprising phytoplankton, zooplankton, micronekton, and top predators^{20–22}. A variant of this model called SEAPODYM Low and Mid Trophic Levels (SEAPODYM-LMTL) has been used to generate 2D fields of micronekton biomass, which are included with the CMEMS product *Global Ocean low and mid trophic levels biomass content hindcast*, GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_BGC_001_033.

The present study presents the first step of a new effort to link ecosystems and biogeochemistry by coupling SEAPODYM-LMTL with the biogeochemical model PISCES²³, which represents carbon fluxes across lower trophic levels up to mesozooplankton, and organic matter exchanges. Using a 1D framework representing a water column, we implemented a one-way coupling in which PISCES provides biogeochemical forcing variables for SEAPODYM-LMTL. Originally, SEAPODYM-LMTL modelled energy transfer from net primary production (NPP) to micronekton functional groups, referred to as Bottom Energy Transfer (BET). To improve the representation of micronekton's trophic interactions, we developed an Intermediate Energy Transfer (IET) version of SEAPODYM-LMTL 1D, where micronekton derive their energy from mesozooplankton or detritus provided by PISCES – i.e., modelled analogues of real-world prey items - rather than from NPP.

In this section, we introduce the implementation of the 1-way coupling between PISCES and SEAPODYM-LMTL IET in 1D, in the context of micronekton biomass estimation. We compare the results to the 1-way coupling with SEAPODYM-LMTL BET, which is driven by NPP. A set of 1D simulations conducted at various discrete locations are used to test the implementation. The goal is to determine whether a refined representation of trophic interactions improves biomass estimations. In the long term, developing a two-way coupling (e.g., considering micronekton's feedback on its environment, such as mesozooplankton and detritus consumption, faecal pellet production, and organic matter deposition) will enable a more comprehensive analysis of micronekton's role in biogeochemical cycles. The work forms the basis for runs with two-way coupling with biogeochemistry, and 1D runs for different biophysical provinces²⁴.

5.2 One-way interactions with biogeochemistry

5.2.1 Background

In SEAPODYM-LMTL, population dynamics (growth, aging, and mortality) and spatial distribution are influenced by temperature and horizontal currents respectively (Lehodey et al., 2010, 2015). The model derives energy for six functional groups of micronekton from vertically integrated net primary production (NPP), referred to as Bottom Energy Transfer (BET). The water column is divided into three vertical pelagic layers based on the euphotic depth (Z_{eu}), with each functional group occupying specific layers during the day and night, reflecting distinct migratory behaviours.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

For simplicity, this study reduces the vertical structure to two pelagic layers derived from SEAPODYM-LMTL's original three layers:

- Epipelagic layer (L_{epi}): Extending from the surface to $1.5 \times Zeu$ (~0-150 m).
- Mesopelagic layer (L_{meso}): Extending from $1.5 \times Zeu$ to $10.5 \times Zeu$ (~150-1000 m).

The six original functional groups are consolidated into three simplified groups:

- Epipelagic group: Residents of the epipelagic layer.
- Migrant group: Migrating between the epipelagic layer at night and the mesopelagic layer during the day.
- Mesopelagic group: Residents of the mesopelagic layer.

To enhance the coupling with the biogeochemical model PISCES and better represent biogeochemical processes, we developed a mechanistic approach to model micronekton's trophic interactions. While the original SEAPODYM-LMTL used Bottom Energy Transfer (BET), with NPP as the direct energy source for micronekton, we have developed an Intermediate Energy Transfer (IET) version. In IET, micronekton receives energy from mesozooplankton or detritus provided by PISCES, rather than from NPP. Drawing from the literature, we established the following assumptions to model trophic interactions in IET:

- Epipelagic micronekton feeds on mesozooplankton ²⁵.
- Migratory micronekton also feeds on mesozooplankton, but only during nocturnal migrations to the epipelagic layer ^{25,26}.
- Mesopelagic micronekton consumes small and large sinking particles ^{25,27,28}.

5.2.2 Theory

This study introduces a 1D version of SEAPODYM-LMTL (both BET and IET), modelling a simplified water column extending from the surface to the ocean bottom. Unlike the 3D version, this approach omits advection and diffusion, leading to simplified equations. The biomass' sink and source terms for the 1D model is:

$$\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} = -\lambda B + P(\tau_r)$$

(4)

where $\lambda(T)$ is the micronekton mortality rate (days^{-1}) and $\tau_r(T)$ is the micronekton recruitment age (days), both depending on the ambient temperature T . These two parameters govern the growing processes in SEAPODYM-LMTL. The reaction term $-\lambda B$ describes the mortality of B (i.e., sink corresponding to the dying fraction of the biomass). The source term $P(\tau_r)$ represents the recruitment process.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Micronekton production $P(\tau_r)$ denotes the recruitment of organisms reaching adulthood, into the foraging population B (biomass, gC/m^2). The recruitment time τ_r (days) depends on water temperature, inspired by Gillooly et al. (2002). The model discretizes micronekton age into uniform cohorts, each representing a constant age interval. The number of cohorts is determined by the maximum recruitment time $\tau_{r\max}$ divided by the simulation time step. The first age cohort ($\tau = 0$) of micronekton production is computed using an equation which links the energy source to micronekton production. For Bottom Energy Transfer (BET), where NPP directly drives production, the initial condition is:

$$P(\tau = 0) = E_{BET} E'_n NPP \quad (5)$$

where E_{BET} is the energy transfer coefficient between primary production and micronekton and E'_n represents the redistribution coefficients across the n functional groups (the sum of which equals 1, both coefficient dimensionless). NPP is the surface Net Primary Production (gC m^{-2}).

The ageing process $\frac{\partial P}{\partial t}$ progresses by shifting production to subsequent age classes, with age and time discretized using identical steps (7 days in this study, both for IET and BET).

In the Intermediate Energy Transfer (IET) model, micronekton production depends on the functional group:

- Epipelagic micronekton: $P(\tau = 0) = E_{IET\ zpk} E'_n \int_0^{z_{L\text{epi}}} M(z) dz$
- Migrant micronekton: $P(\tau = 0) = E_{IET\ zpk} E'_n \frac{24-DL}{24} \int_0^{z_{L\text{epi}}} M(z) dz$
- Mesopelagic micronekton: $P(\tau = 0) = E_{IET\ detritus} E'_n \int_{z_{L\text{epi}}}^{z_{L\text{meso}}} (GOC(z) + POC(z)) dz$

with $z_{L\text{epi}}$ the epipelagic layer depth (m), $z_{L\text{meso}}$ the mesopelagic layer depth (m), M the mesozooplankton biomass (gC m^{-2}), GOC the large sinking particles (gC m^{-2}), POC the small sinking particles (gC m^{-2}), and DL the day length (hours).

The energy transfer coefficient E needs to be reconsidered between BET and IET version. In the BET version, this parameter represents the energy transfer between primary production and micronekton (E_{BET}). In the IET version, it represents the energy transfer between zooplankton and micronekton for the epipelagic and migrant functional groups ($E_{IET\ zpk}$), and between detritus and micronekton for the mesopelagic functional group ($E_{IET\ detritus}$).

5.2.3 Implementation

The IET version of SEAPODYM-LMTL has been developed from scratch as a new model in Fortran in the FABM framework (<https://github.com/neccton-algo/SEAPODYM-1D-IET>), using FABM coding conventions (see D3.1).

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 8 Micronekton biomasses simulated using 1D GOTM-FABM-PISCES-SEAPODYM-LMTL runs are presented for both BET and IET versions (indicated in green and yellow, respectively). The 1D model was applied at a fixed location in the Tasman Sea, covering the period from 2010 to 2020. Biomasses for the three functional micronekton groups are shown: epipelagic (top panels), migrant (middle panels), and mesopelagic (bottom panels) in gC m⁻².

Parameters are specified in the fabm.yaml file. For an example, see: <https://github.com/neccton-algo/SEAPODYM-1D-IET/blob/main/fabm.yaml>.

5.2.4 Testing

A set of 1D simulations conducted at several fixed-point locations are used to test the implementation using 1D GOTM 1D water column set ups. In this deliverable, we focus on the

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 9 As in Figure 8 but showing monthly climatological values.

example of the Tasman Sea. We ran 10-year simulations of 1D GOTM-FABM-PISCES-SEAPODYM-LMTL IET and BET, with a daily timestep.

We compare the outputs in micronekton biomass for the three functional groups: epipelagic, migrant and mesopelagic (Figure 8 and Figure 9). The magnitudes of IET biomasses outputs depends on the parametrization of the energy transfer coefficient, E , which is uncertain. Here, we scale the results with those of the BET simulation and focus on seasonality which is independent of the magnitude.

We observe that for both epipelagic and migrant micronekton, seasonality is weaker in the biomass derived from IET compared to BET, with a slight temporal lag between the two. This is expected, as zooplankton biomass, which drives IET, typically exhibits weaker seasonality than the NPP driving BET. Additionally, a temporal lag is anticipated between phytoplankton blooms and the zooplankton biomass peaks.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

For validation, we searched for micronekton data with sufficient spatio-temporal resolution to observe the seasonal cycle. Between La Réunion and Kerguelen, acoustic transects are highly frequent, with repeated back-and-forth trips by fishing vessels equipped with calibrated EK80 sonars. From these transects, an annual cycle can be reconstructed, allowing the identification of a seasonality cycle. To compare and determine which version, IET or BET, most accurately reproduces the seasonal cycle observed in the acoustic data, 1D simulations were conducted at three different locations between La Réunion and Kerguelen.

To our knowledge, very few studies have focused on micronekton seasonality, and none have explored it using models. This remains a largely understudied aspect, highlighting the need for dedicated efforts in this field. By addressing this gap, we position ourselves as pioneers in advancing the understanding of micronekton seasonal dynamics. This analysis will provide valuable insights into the timing and amplitude of micronekton biomass seasonality based on observational data. It is particularly important for improving our global understanding of marine ecosystems and for fisheries management, as it helps predict resource availability and ecosystem dynamics more accurately.

6 Suspended Particulate Matter

6.1 Introduction

Suspended particulate matter (SPM) is a collective term for the inorganic (e.g., mineral) and organic (e.g., detritus; see next section) particulates that are suspended in the water column. It is an indicator of sediment transport, water clarity and quality; and has important implications for pelagic and benthic productivity and erosion. It can also act as a vector for the transfers of pollutants and contaminants. In NECCTON, we have implemented support for simulating SPM. A new SPM module has been developed for the fine-scale, unstructured hydrodynamic model SHYFEM-MPI. The model was tested in 3D using a local, high-resolution model domain for the Tyrrhenian Sea. This module was then rewritten for FABM and incorporated into the ERSEM model, where it will support the delivery of a new SPM product for the Northwest European Shelf domain. A separate model of SPM was developed for BAMHBI, where it was run with NEMO to study the transport of organic SPM in the Black Sea.

In this section, we describe the processes governing SPM dynamics and their implementation in the three different models. The SPM SHYFEM-MPI and BAMHBI SPM models are tested in 3D. The FABM implementation, which is a port of the SPM SHYFEM-MPI model, is tested using a combination of PyFABM and 1-D simulations, where PyFABM is a tool which allows one to call study model behaviour in a 0D setting.

6.2 Suspended Particulate Matter Dynamics

6.2.1 Background

Even after putting aside suspended particles of biological origin, marine sediments are extremely diverse and are found in a wide range of different sizes and shapes, and with varying composition. It

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

is common to categorise particles according to their physical size – a property which strongly influences a particle’s transport dynamics.

Table 4 Grain classification based on grain size ²⁹.

Type	Clast name	Size range
Coarse grained (gravel) Non-cohesive	Boulder	> 256 mm
	Cobble	64 mm – 256 mm
	Pebble	4 mm – 64 mm
	Granule	2 mm – 4 mm
Medium grained (sand) Non-cohesive	Coarse	500 μm – 2 mm
	Medium	250 μm – 500 μm
	Fine	63 μm – 250 μm
Fine grained (mud) Cohesive	Silt	2 μm – 63 μm
	Clay	< 2 μm

Table 4 summarises the major inorganic sediment classes, which are grouped according to their grain size. Particles measuring > 2 mm in size are classed as gravel, which includes small granules and pebbles, and also large cobbles and boulders. Due to their large size, gravels are not typically carried in suspension, but may move from location to location through rolling, sliding and hopping along the bed (saltation). Sand particles vary in size from 63 μm up to 2 mm and are readily moved in suspension – especially the smaller size fractions. Sand particles are deemed to be non-cohesive, which means individual grains behave independently to other sand grains. This contrasts with marine muds, which includes silt and clay particles that are smaller than 63 μm in size. In suspension, electrostatic forces cause mud particles to aggregate at a sufficiently high concentration, forming larger flocs which can have markedly different transport properties to the constituent particles from which they are formed. In the bed, these same cohesive forces can impede erosion and make the bed more resistant to scour. In mixed beds, and in the water column, the transport dynamics of sand grains can be impacted by the presence of mud. However, understanding of these interactions, and of the important role biological material plays, is less developed than what it is for pure mixtures.

Figure 10 summarises the key processes involved in the transport of both non-cohesive and cohesive sediments that have been implemented in the new SHYFEM-MPI model of SPM dynamics. For non-cohesive sediments, these include sinking, deposition and resuspension. For cohesive sediments, a parameterisation of flocculation in the water column and the sinking of flocs is also included. A relatively simple model of the bed is included, which has been developed within WP6: it is treated as a single layer, which may contain a varying mixture of sand and mud. The model does not attempt to represent multiple layers with varying physical properties, sediment consolidation within the bed, time varying bathymetry, or bed load transport. Implementing support for modelling these processes were deemed to be outside the scope of the current project.

In contrast, the BHAMBI SPM model focusses on the organic component of SPM. Many of the processes controlling the movement of organic SPM are the same as those controlling the movement

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 10 SPM processes implemented in the SPM model

of inorganic SPM. In the BAMHBI model, the additional impact of waves on the bottom shear stress is considered (see Table 5).

6.2.2 Theory

The SPM model includes three fundamental processes: vertical sinking, deposition, and erosion (Figure 10). These processes are modelled differently for cohesive and non-cohesive sediment.

Sinking of non-cohesive particles

Non-cohesive particles sink at a rate w_s . The sinking rate can either be set for a given class of particles based on the result of empirical studies, or it can be calculated as a function of environmental conditions and particle properties using mechanistic formulae. If the sinking rate is to be calculated, the particle's density and size must be specified. We follow the method of Soulsby³⁰, to derive the sinking rate of particles. The sinking rate is given by the equation:

$$w_s = \frac{\nu}{d} \left((10.36^2 + 1.049D_*^3)^{\frac{1}{2}} - 10.36 \right) \quad (6)$$

where ν is the kinematic viscosity of sea water ($m^2 s^{-1}$), d is the grain diameter (m), and D_* is the dimensionless grain size. ν is given by the equation:

$$\nu = \frac{\mu}{\rho_o} \quad (7)$$

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Table 5 Summary of model test configuration for SPM.

Model	Inorganic or Organic?	Wave coupling?	Test configuration	Test location
SPM	Inorganic	No	SPM with SHYFEM-MPI	Tyrrhenian Sea (3D)
BHAMBI	Organic	Yes	BHAMBI with NEMO	Black Sea (3D)
ERSEM	Inorganic	No	ERSEM with GOTM	Station L4 (1D)

where μ is the dynamic viscosity (Pa s) and ρ_o is the density of sea water (kg m^{-3}). ρ_o is taken directly from the hydrodynamic model, while μ is calculated from temperature and salinity ³¹.

The dimensionless grain diameter D_* is calculated using the expression:

$$D_* = \left(\frac{g(1-s)}{v^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} d \quad (8)$$

where g is acceleration due to gravity ($= 9.81 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$); s is the ratio of the densities of grains (ρ_s) and water; and d is the grain diameter. The expression for the sinking velocity of non-cohesive sand grains has been compared with 115 measurements of sinking velocities of natural sands and irregular shaped light weight grains ³⁰. Using this expression, 90 % of the predictions lie within 20 % of the measured value.

Sinking of cohesive particles

The behaviour of suspended mud is more complex than that of sand, with sinking rates dependent on the local concentration. In saline waters, when the dry mass concentration of cohesive particles C_{M_c} is greater than approximately 0.01 kg m^{-3} , mud particles begin to flocculate. Flocs form when grains collide and become stuck together, which can happen due to differential settling and turbulent shear. The size of the flocs increases with the mass concentration, which increases the likelihood of collisions. The size and sinking velocity of the floc can be much larger than that of its constituent grains; and it is important to account for the impact of flocculation on particle sinking rates, especially when the sediment concentration is higher than 0.01 kg m^{-3} .

The approach for computing the sinking velocity of flocs is dependent on the total concentration of cohesive sediments in the water column. Below the concentration limit C_{flim1} , hindered settling is not modelled, and the sinking velocity of cohesive particles w_{fs} is calculated using the simplified expression:

$$w_{fs} = kC_{M_c}^m \quad (9)$$

where k and m are empirically derived parameters. For $C_{flim1} < C_{M_c}^m \leq C_{flim2}$, we follow the approach of Whitehouse ³², and compute the median settling velocity of flocs as a function of the concentration of suspended mud using the equation:

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

$$w_{fs} = \frac{v}{d_{fe}} \left((10.36^2 + 1.049(1 - C_f)^{4.7} D_{f*}^3)^{\frac{1}{2}} - 10.36 \right) \quad (10)$$

where d_{fe} is the effective floc diameter, C_f is the volume concentration of flocs in sea water, and D_{f*} is the dimensionless floc diameter. d_{fe} is taken to be a function of the volume concentration of the suspension, C , and is given by the expression:

$$d_{fe} = l C^{\frac{m}{2}} \quad (11)$$

where l is a length scale and m is a power coefficient which is identical to that used in Equation (9). The length-scale, l , is given by the relationship:

$$l = \left(\frac{19.8 \rho_w v \rho_s^m k}{g(\rho_{fe} - \rho_o)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (12)$$

where ρ_{fe} is the effective density of the floc, ρ_s is the mineral density of grains (the same symbol is used for sand), and k is a second coefficient which must be empirically determined. ρ_{fe} is given by the expression:

$$\rho_{fe} = \rho_w + C_{in}(\rho_s - \rho_o) \quad (13)$$

where C_{in} is the internal volume concentration of grains inside a floc and is a parameter which must be set by the user. Its value is observed to vary in the range 0.025 – 0.04.

Returning to Equation (10), the volume concentration of flocs in water, C_f , is given by the equation:

$$C_f = \frac{(\rho_s - \rho_o) C}{(\rho_e - \rho_o)} \quad (14)$$

and the dimensionless floc diameter is given by the equation:

$$D_{f*} = \left(\frac{g(\rho_e - \rho_o)}{\rho_o v^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} d_{fe} \quad (15)$$

For $C_{flim2} < C_{M_c}^m \leq C_{flim3}$, we use a simpler formulation proposed ³³:

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

$$w_{fs} = 0.00462(1 - 0.01C_{M_c})^{3.54} \quad (16)$$

For $C_{M_c}^m > C_{flim3}$, $w_{fs} = 1 \times 10^{-5}$.

Calculation of bottom stress

To model sediment dynamics near to the bed, including the processes of deposition and erosion, the bottom stress must be provided by the hydrodynamic model or calculated. With combined wave-current flows, the impact of both must be combined. The bottom stress from currents is calculated with the quadratic friction law:

$$\tau_c = \rho_o c_d U^2 \quad (17)$$

where U is the absolute velocity, and c_d is the drag coefficient. Assuming a logarithmic current profile, the drag coefficient can be computed as a spatially varying value based on the thickness of the lowest water layer Δz_{bottom} and the roughness length z_0 (dependent on median grain size):

$$c_d = \kappa^{-2} \left[1 + \ln \left(\frac{z_0}{\Delta z_{bottom}} \right) \right]^{-2} \quad (18)$$

where $\kappa = 0.41$ is the von Kármán constant. Alternatively, c_d can be set to a constant value, such as 10^{-3} in the NEMO model (nonlinear bottom drag option). While the spatially varying formulation allows for a more accurate representation of sediment composition, using a constant value ensures consistency between physical and biogeochemical model components.

The bottom stress from waves is computed as:

$$\tau_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho_o f_w U_w^2 \quad (19)$$

where f_w is the wave friction coefficient and U_w is the maximum horizontal orbital wave velocity. Following Soulsby (Soulsby, R. L. "Dynamics of Marine Sands." (1997).), U_w can be computed from wave model variables (significant wave height H , mean wave period T , and wave number k):

$$U_w = \frac{\pi H}{T \sinh(kh)} \quad (20)$$

where h is the water depth. The wave friction coefficient f_w depends on the Reynolds number R_w and flow regime. It is computed as:

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

$$f_w = \max(f_{wr}, f_{ws}) \quad (21)$$

where f_{wr} is the rough bed friction:

$$f_{wr} = 0.237 \left(\frac{A}{k_s} \right)^{-0.52} \quad (22)$$

with orbital amplitude $A = \frac{U_w T}{2\pi}$ and bed roughness $k_s = 2.5d_{50}$ (d_{50} being the median grain size). The smooth bed friction f_{ws} is:

$$f_{ws} = BR_w^{-N} \quad (23)$$

where for laminar flow ($R_w < 5 \times 10^5$), $B = 2$, $N = 0.5$; and for turbulent flow ($R_w \geq 5 \times 10^5$), $B = 0.0521$, $N = 0.187$.

The total bottom stress is computed as the vector sum of current and wave bottom shear stress, accounting for their angular difference. Wave-current interaction creates a non-linear enhancement of the bottom stress, which is calculated using empirical formulas. We use the formulation by Soulsby (1997). The mean current stress including wave enhancement is:

$$\tau_{\text{mean}} = \tau_c \left[1 + 1.2 \left(\frac{\tau_w}{\tau_w + \tau_c} \right)^{3.2} \right] \quad (24)$$

The total bottom shear stress incorporating the angular difference Φ between wave and current directions is computed as a vector sum:

$$\tau = \sqrt{(\tau_{\text{mean}} + \tau_w \cos(\Phi))^2 + (\tau_w \sin(\Phi))^2} \quad (25)$$

For the angular difference Φ , a coordinate system conversion is required as wave and current directions use different conventions. Wave angles in common wave data (including CMEMS products) follow the ECMWF convention where 0° indicates waves coming from the north and 90° from the east. Current angles in ocean circulation models use 0° for currents coming from the west (in u-direction). Current direction is computed as $\arctan 2(v, u)$ with values between $-\pi$ and π . Wave angles are transformed to the current reference system by subtracting 90° , converting from the range $0-360^\circ$ to $(-180^\circ, 180^\circ)$, inverting from clockwise to counterclockwise rotation, and converting to radians.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

The minimum angular difference between wave and current directions can thus be computed as:

$$\Phi = |(\phi_w - \phi_c + \pi) \bmod 2\pi - \pi| \quad (26)$$

Deposition

Deposition refers to the settling out of sediment and its deposition on the bed. In still water, the rate of deposition of sediment from suspension dm/dt can be modelled using the near-bed concentration of suspended sediment C_b and the median settling velocity of particles w_s :

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = -C_b w_s \quad (27)$$

In the presence of flowing water or waves, near-bed turbulence can hinder deposition, especially of fine particles. This effect can be accounted for by defining a critical bed shear stress for deposition τ_d which is the bed stress above which deposition does not occur. In the presence of flowing water, this effect can be modelled using the expression:

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = \begin{cases} -(1 - \tau_0/\tau_d)C_b w_s & \text{for } \tau_0 < \tau_d \\ 0 & \text{for } \tau_0 \geq \tau_d \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

where τ_0 is the bed-shear stress in the presence of flowing water. In the presence of flowing water and waves, τ_0 must be replaced by a term which accounts for their combined impact on the bed shear stress. τ_d is a parameter which must be determined empirically for different grain types. In the models, the user is given the choice of whether to define and use τ_d , or simply model deposition using Equation (27).

Erosion

Erosion is the process by which sediment deposited on the bed is eroded by currents and wave action. A threshold bed shear-stress for erosion τ_e is used to define the bed-shear stress above which erosion occurs. In the real world, it is a function of the grain type and the bed composition. For sand, several approaches for calculating the bed shear stress from the properties of grains have been proposed. The threshold bed shear-stress for a given grain type can also be derived from laboratory experiments and used as a parameter in models. Here we describe two popular models, which have been implemented within NECCTON: The Soulsby Method³⁴, and The van Rijn Method³⁵. In addition, an option to specify the threshold bed-shear stress for erosion as a parameter has also been included. For beds containing a mixture of sand and mud, a further modification of the bed shear-stress is included to reflect the impact of sediment cohesion on bed erosion.

6.2.2.1.1 The Soulsby Method

In the Soulsby Method, the critical bed shear-stress for sand grains is given by the expression:

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

$$\tau_e = gd(\rho_s - \rho_w)\theta_{cr}$$

(29)

where g , d , ρ_s , and ρ_w are as defined for sinking; and θ_{cr} is the threshold Shields parameter. Based on fits to data Soulsby and Whitehouse³⁴, derived the following expression for θ_{cr} :

$$\theta_{cr} = \frac{0.3}{1 + 1.2D_*} + 0.055(1 - e^{-0.02D_*})$$

(30)

6.2.2.1.2 The van Rijn Method

The van Rijn method differs only in the approach for calculating θ_{cr} as a function of D_* :

$$\theta_{cr} = \begin{cases} 2.4 \times 10^{-1} D_*^{-0.90} & \text{for } D_* \leq 4 \\ 1.4 \times 10^{-1} D_*^{-0.64} & \text{for } 4 < D_* \leq 10 \\ 4.0 \times 10^{-2} D_*^{-0.10} & \text{for } 10 < D_* \leq 20 \\ 1.3 \times 10^{-2} D_*^{-0.29} & \text{for } 20 < D_* \leq 150 \\ 5.6 \times 10^{-2} & \text{for } D_* > 150 \end{cases}$$

(31)

6.2.2.1.3 Mud-sand mixtures

The Soulsby and van Rijn methods for calculating the threshold Shields parameter are specific to sandy beds. Muddy beds tend to be harder to erode due to the cohesive forces between particles. For mixed beds with a mud content greater than approximately 15 %, cohesive effects start to become important. To account for this effect, we follow the approach of van Rijn by including a dependency on the mud content p_c of the bed^{33,36}. Defining the percentage mud content as:

$$p_c = \frac{m_c}{m_t}$$

(32)

where m_c is the mass of cohesive sediment within the bed, and m_t is the total mass of sediment in the bed. The threshold bed shear-stress for erosion and including cohesive effects $\tau_{e,c}$ is then calculated using the equation:

$$\tau_{e,c} = \tau_e(1 + p_c)^\beta$$

(33)

In early work, the parameter β was assigned a value in the range 1.5 – 3. In later studies, it was observed to vary with the percentage of clay and fines in the bed, and the dry bulk density³⁷. However, for simplicity, we maintain the original formulation, in which β is assigned a fixed value.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Table 6 Common SPM parameters, their units and reference values.

Parameter	Description	Units	Reference value
ϵ	Bed porosity	-	0.4
β	Beta exponent for erosion	-	2
K	Constant used in Equation (9)	-	1×10^{-3}
m	Constant used in Equation (9)	-	1
C_{in}	Internal volume concentration of grains inside a floc	-	3×10^{-2}
C_{flim1}	Mass concentration limit 1 for flocculation and settling calculation	kg m ⁻³	2
C_{flim2}	Mass concentration limit 2 for flocculation and settling calculation	kg m ⁻³	50
C_{flim3}	Mass concentration limit 3 for flocculation and settling calculation	kg m ⁻³	82
m_1	Parameter governing the mass per unit area eroded	kg m ⁻²	5×10^{-3}
m_2	Parameter controlling the rate of erosion at low bed concentrations	-	1×10^{-5}

6.2.2.1.4 Erosion flux

The actual erosion flux is calculated using the formulation of Ariathurai and Arulanandan³⁸, which is also described in³⁹.

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = m_e \left(\frac{\tau_0}{\tau_{e,c}} - 1 \right) (1 - \epsilon) \quad (34)$$

where ϵ is the bed's porosity, and m_e is an erosion coefficient that is given by the function:

$$m_e = \min (m_1, m_2 m) \quad (35)$$

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Here, m_1 is the bed erosion content, which can vary by orders of magnitude between locations. m_2 is a second constant which introduces a first order dependence on the amount of material in the bed at low concentrations.

6.2.3 Implementation

Support for SPM modelling has been added to three separate models: the SHYFEM-MPI hydrodynamic model, BAMHBI and ERSEM. The ERSEM SPM code is a port of the SPM SHYFEM-MPI code, which involved rewriting the module to utilise the FABM library. Common parameters for the models are listed in Table 6. Links to the code are provided in Table 2.

SHYFEM-MPI

The SPM model has been integrated as a FORTRAN module into SHYFEM-MPI⁴⁰, the MPI implementation of the three-dimensional finite element hydrodynamic model SHYFEM. To solve the equations presented above, the SHYFEM-MPI model provides the SPM module with temperature and salinity fields as well as bottom stress. Parameters are specified in a single parameter file.

ERSEM

The model of SPM that was created and tested with the SHYFEM-MPI model was reimplemented in the ERSEM codebase. The model was rewritten using FABM coding conventions (see NECCTON D3.1). The implementation includes new types for non-cohesive and cohesive particles. These enable one to run the model with any number of non-cohesive and cohesive particle classes. A small number of ancillary modules provide supporting functionality. To use SPM in an ERSEM model run, one or more SPM tracers must be specified in the file ERSEM *fabm.yaml*. An example ERSEM *fabm.yaml* file can be found in the git repository: <https://github.com/pmlmodelling/ersem-spm-setup>.

BHAMBI

The BAMHBI Black Sea implementation of sediment resuspension due to currents and waves is based on the NEMO-BAMHBI setup (CMEMS Dataset: CMEMS BLKSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_007_010).

6.2.4 Testing

In this section we describe the results of test simulations performed using the three SPM models.

SPM with SHYFEM-MPI

The numerical model has been implemented and validated for the Tyrrhenian Sea coastal region adjacent to Civitavecchia, Italy (Figure 11, 42.15°N, 11.75°E). We selected this geographical domain for its heterogeneous bathymetric characteristics, pronounced sedimentological gradients, and

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 11 SHYFEM-MPI domain in the Tyrrhenian Sea. Model domain and bathymetry are shown on the left and Seabed EMODnet type in Civitavecchia domain (black line) on the right.

diverse benthic habitat distribution, making it well suited for evaluating suspended sediment transport dynamics.

The domain extends 65 km along the coastline and 20 km offshore, encompassing both the littoral zone and the continental shelf. The bathymetric profile exhibits significant variability, ranging from shallow coastal environments to shelf depths of approximately 220 m, thereby incorporating multiple hydrodynamic regimes relevant to sediment transport processes. The horizontal mesh resolution has been spatially varied, with maximum refinement ($\Delta x \approx 100$ m) in the coastal zone where bathymetric gradients and sediment dynamics require enhanced spatial resolution. The mesh gradually coarsens to approximately 1.5 km in offshore regions where spatial gradients are less pronounced. Vertical discretization has been achieved through 43 z-levels with thickness varying from 1 m at the surface to larger intervals at depth, ensuring adequate resolution of both the surface mixed layer and bottom boundary layer processes critical for sediment transport.

We performed a two-year simulation (2020-2021) after a three-year spin-up period to achieve dynamical equilibrium in the physical components. The simulation has been forced by hourly surface atmospheric variables from the ERA5 reanalysis⁸. We conducted the hydrodynamic initialization using three-dimensional fields of temperature, salinity, and currents from the CMEMS Mediterranean Sea Physical Reanalysis system⁴¹. For the benthic and pelagic SPM, we used the Seabed Habitats dataset (Figure 11b, <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/seabed-habitats>), to identify sediment classes and create initial spatial distribution of each sediment class. We identified three distinct granulometric classes: the first class comprises cohesive mud particles with a characteristic diameter of 40 μm , incorporating flocculation processes. The second class represents non-cohesive fine sand with an 80 μm diameter, governed by individual particle dynamics. A third class with 0.1 m diameter has been implemented to represent rocky substrates, functioning as a passive benthic boundary without participating in erosion-deposition cycles.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 12 Model domain showing the unstructured mesh and monitoring stations used for model validation. A scale bar and north arrow are provided for reference. Right: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) analysis for Sea Surface Temperature (SST, top panel) and Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM, bottom panel) at each monitoring station for the period 2020-2021. RMSE values are calculated comparing model outputs with ESA SST CCI observations for SST and CMEMS Global Sea Level-3 SPM product for SPM concentrations.

The spatial heterogeneity of benthic sediment distributions has been reconstructed as follows (referring to Figure 12b): we characterized fine mud environments by an 80:20 ratio of mud to fine sand, while we initialized sandy substrates with the inverse proportion. Mixed sedimentary facies, including muddy sand and sandy mud classifications, have been configured with equal proportions of both constituents. The initial sediment distribution has been parameterized with a uniform mass density of 660 kg m^{-2} across the seabed, corresponding to a 0.25 m thickness assuming a characteristic sediment density of 2650 kg m^{-3} . Each grid point has a total of 660 kg m^{-2} of sediment to be divided among the sediment classes. We defined the initial condition of each sediment class upon the previous seabed type partition table; for example, a grid point in "Fine mud" type contained 480 kg m^{-2} in the mud class and 120 kg m^{-2} in the sand one. Initial suspended particulate matter concentrations in the water column (i.e., pelagic system) have been set to zero to allow the development of realistic spatial distributions through physical transport mechanisms. Lateral open boundary conditions for the suspended sediments have been prescribed from CMEMS MED Reanalysis data ⁴¹for the physics and from CMEMS GlobalSea Level-3 SPM product based on the Copernicus-GlobColour product (CMEMS product OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_BGC_L3_MY_009_103) for the sediment classes. As a first simplistic approach, we split satellite SPM data equally between the two classes and distributed them homogeneously downward.

Model performance evaluation has been conducted through quantitative comparison of simulated and observed SST and SPM (i.e., sum of the mud and sand concentrations) at multiple reference stations distributed throughout the domain (Figure 12b). The SPM model has been validated using the CMEMS Global Sea Level-3 SPM product, while the hydrodynamic model skill has been assessed using Level 4 sea surface temperature data, available via the Copernicus Climate Data Store, which provides high-resolution (0.05°) daily satellite observations ⁴².

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 13 Time series comparison of modeled (blue line) and observed (black dots) total SPM concentrations (MUD + SAND) at four representative stations during 2020-2021. (a) Station 3-CTD showing coastal dynamics (RMSE=1.74 g m⁻³, n=516); (b) Station SPM-N demonstrating offshore behaviour (RMSE=0.66 g m⁻³, n=512); (c) Station IT_m1vt04_12 representing transitional waters (RMSE=0.75 g m⁻³, n=521); and (d) Station SPM-S capturing southern domain characteristics (RMSE=0.90 g m⁻³, n=519). RMSE values and number of observations (n) are reported for each station.

The RMSE analysis (Figure 12b) reveals consistent model performance across all monitoring stations. For SST, we observed RMSE values ranging between 0.6°C and 1.0°C, with the best performance at coastal stations (e.g., SPM-S with RMSE = 0.62°C) and slightly higher values at offshore locations (e.g., CTD-3 with RMSE = 1.05°C). These values are within the expected range for regional coastal models and indicate robust hydrodynamic performance.

SPM simulations show varying degrees of accuracy across the domain, with RMSE values ranging from (0.66 - 2.2) g m⁻³. The lowest RMSE values have been found at stations SPM-S (0.65 g m⁻³) and SPM-C (0.75 g m⁻³), indicating particularly good model performance in reproducing suspended sediment dynamics in these areas. Higher RMSE values at stations closer to the coast (e.g., CTD-2 and CTD-3 with RMSE > 1.7 g m⁻³) reflect the increased complexity of sediment dynamics in nearshore environments, where interactions between waves, currents, and bathymetry lead to more variable SPM concentrations.

Time series analysis at selected stations (Figure 13) provides additional insights into model performance. At station 3-CTD, despite an RMSE of 1.74 g m⁻³, the model successfully captures the temporal evolution of SPM peaks, particularly during high-concentration events (>4 g m⁻³). The SPM-N station shows excellent agreement between modelled and observed concentrations (RMSE = 0.66 g m⁻³), with the model accurately reproducing both the timing and magnitude of concentration variations. At station IT_m1vt04_12, we observed good correlation between simulated and observed patterns, with an RMSE of 0.75 g m⁻³, although some peak concentrations are slightly underestimated. The SPM-S station time series (RMSE = 0.90 g m⁻³) demonstrates the model's capability to capture

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 14 Model results from NEMO-BHAMBI, using a configuration for the Black Sea. Show is the mean bottom stress on the North Western Black Sea Shelf (left); the contribution of waves to the total bottom stress (centre); and the frequency of resuspension events throughout year (right).

seasonal variations in SPM concentrations particularly evident in the winter months when increased wave activity enhances sediment resuspension.

The number of observations for each station ($n \approx 515-521$) provides a robust statistical basis for the validation. From these comprehensive analyses, we can conclude that the SPM model demonstrates good skill in reproducing the SPM variability in the Civitavecchia coastal area, with particularly strong performance in capturing temporal patterns and seasonal variations. The slightly higher RMSE values near the coast are consistent with the inherent complexity of coastal sediment dynamics and the challenges in representing highly variable nearshore processes.

BHAMBI implementation

Preliminary experiments at $1/6^\circ$ resolution over the period 1990-2023 revealed that wave coupling significantly affects bottom stress in the shallowest areas of the Black Sea Northwestern shelf, where most sediment resuspension occurs (Figure 14), particularly during fall and winter. This setup used a static threshold of 0.02 Pa for resuspension, as the SHYFEM based variable critical bottom stress module has not yet been implemented in NEMO-BAMHBI. Currently, the setup focuses only on the resuspension of particulate organic matter, with mineral particulate matter to be included in future developments.

Including resuspension-driven suspended matter dynamics in NEMO-BAMHBI led to significant differences in the biogeochemical model when waves were included. Comparison of three simulation types (with wave and current resuspension, with current-only resuspension, and without resuspension) revealed that current-only and no-resuspension simulations produced similar results, as bottom currents alone were insufficient to trigger resuspension. Wave-induced resuspension increased the average POM concentration in the shelf water column by approximately 30 %. Through remineralization of this organic material, wave-induced resuspension also led to a comparable increase in shelf nutrient concentrations.

A technical consideration is the high inertia of sediments in NEMO-BAMHBI, which can extend up to 10 years. This necessitates adequately long model spin-up times when modifying parameters that affect sediment dynamics.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 15 Hovmoller plots of SPM concentrations at Station L4 in the Western English Channel, which have been simulated using a 1D configuration of GOTM-ERSEM. Shown is the modelled concentration of sand (a) and mud (b).

ERSEM Implementation

The ERSEM-SPM model was tested using a combination of PyFABM and the 1D model GOTM. Notebooks showing the model exactly reproduces published check values for sinking rates are provided in the repository: <https://github.com/pmlmodelling/ersem-spm-setup>. In 1D, a simple test run is produced using a GOTM configuration for Station L4 in the Western English Channel (also available in the *ersem-spm-setup* GitHub repository). Sample output is shown in Figure 15 for a run with two sediment classes: sand particles with a diameter of 80 microns and mud particles with a diameter of 10 microns. The model was initialised with an equal mix of mud and sand in the bed, and a total bed sediment concentration of 2000 kg m^{-2} . The water column was initialised with a concentration of 1 kg m^{-3} of both sand and mud, which was homogeneous throughout the water column. A high, fixed bed stress of 2 Pa was used. This was above the threshold for erosion of both sand and mud particles, given an initial equal mixture within the bed. Over time, both mud and sand are eroded from the bed. We did not impose a threshold bed shear stress for deposition, which allows both sand and mud particles to undergo deposition. Due to the faster sinking rate of the larger sand grains, sand grains are deposited back on the bed at a faster rate, and the concentration of mud in the water column quickly exceeds that of sand. As more mud is eroded from the bed, the bed becomes less cohesive, and erosion rates increase. When turbulent mixing in the water column is more vigorous, as is the case on 12th January, both mud and sand grains are mixed further up the water column. These results are consistent with the mathematical model of SPM dynamics described here.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

7 Particulate Organic Matter

7.1 Introduction

Particulate Organic Matter (POM) in the ocean is operationally defined as all combustible organic matter that can be retained on a filter. The filter mesh size is typically 0.7 μm , although can also be 0.2 μm . It is often discussed in terms of Particulate Organic Carbon (POC), which reflects the important role POC plays in the ocean carbon cycle. The definition explicitly excludes Particulate Inorganic Carbon (PIC). The finite mesh size means the contribution of organisms smaller than 0.7 μm – including most photosynthetic and non-photosynthetic prokaryotes – is not captured in measurements. At the other end of the size spectrum, the contribution of large, motile zooplankton is also not measured. Such organisms are either intentionally removed through filtering, or through sampling techniques which are designed to exclude larger, swimming organisms. The operational definition of POM and POC contrasts with the definition used in most marine ecosystem and biogeochemical models. In marine ecosystem models, POM tends to be exclusively made up of non-living detrital material, including faecal pellets, the bodies of dead organisms, or other aggregations of organic matter. In NECCON, we have enabled the delivery of model total POC, following the operational definition of POC and model detrital POC products for four domains: the Arctic, the Mediterranean Sea, the NW European Shelf and the Baltic Sea. We have improved the underlying models by revisiting how sinking and remineralisation rates are modelled and using recent data from the published literature. These improvements indirectly contribute to the bio-optical modelling through improved representation of detrital matter and thus quantity of POC in the water column. In addition, these will influence the quantity of organic matter reaching the sea-floor.

In this section, we describe the parameterisation of POC sinking and remineralisation and summarise published rates. The models are tested in 1D.

7.2 Sinking and remineralisation of particulate organic carbon

7.2.1 Background

The sinking and remineralisation of detrital POC are important components of the oceanic biological carbon pump. The gravitational settling (sinking) of non-living organic matter within the water column occurs at different speeds depending on its shape, size and composition. Particulate organic matter is also a carbon and nutrient source to bacteria, which remineralize and use the carbon for growth and convert it back into inorganic carbon and nutrients through respiration. Thus, the combination of production, sinking and remineralisation by bacteria contributes to controlling the POC concentrations in the water column.

The oceans are an important sink for anthropogenic carbon: sinking of POC removes carbon from surface waters and thus enables greater uptake of CO_2 by the ocean. Accurate quantification of this flux is vital for climate change predictions. Similarly, remineralisation converts the POC back into dissolved inorganic carbon. The rate of sinking and remineralisation controls the quantity of POC that reaches the deep ocean or sediments where carbon may be stored on long timescales. It has

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

been estimated that the sinking of POC is responsible for 90% of the vertical inorganic carbon gradient found in the ocean ⁴³.

Table 7 Sinking speeds ($m\ d^{-1}$) for different sizes and types of detrital POC calculated from formulas in Cael et al. ⁴⁴.

Size (μm)	All data	Diatoms	Non-diatoms	Ballast	Non-Ballast	Coast	Ocean	Aggregate	Faecal pellet
20	11	10	10	12	9	13	11	10	15
40	17	15	15	20	13	20	17	15	26
60	22	20	19	25	6	27	21	20	36
100	30	28	26	35	22	37	28	27	54
1000	129	129	98	158	89	166	102	110	331

7.2.2 Theory

Sinking detrital particulate organic carbon

The sinking speeds of detrital organic matter can vary greatly within the ocean from less than $1\ m\ d^{-1}$ to greater than $1000\ m\ d^{-1}$. Typically, particles with sinking speeds of less than $10\ m\ d^{-1}$ are referred to as suspended particles; those with sinking speeds less than $20\ m\ d^{-1}$ as slow sinking ⁴⁵; and those with sinking speeds greater than $20\ m\ d^{-1}$ as fast sinking particles ^{45,46}.

There is relatively little data on sinking speeds of POC for different phytoplankton groups/species. More data exists for phytoplankton aggregates and mesozooplankton pellets. One of the most comprehensive datasets is by Cael et al. ⁴⁴. These authors compiled sinking velocity data from numerous data sources and used a Bayesian model to predict sinking velocities based on particle size and composition/origin. The results are summarised in Table 7 for different sizes and compositions of particle.

One key issue is that most observational data was from particles $>60\ \mu m$ in size and biogeochemical models often contain one or two groups of detrital POC corresponding to a smaller size than this. Thus, data below this size will have a high uncertainty associated with it. The velocities predicted by Cael et al., (2021) are generally higher than that used in biogeochemical models within this project, with ERSEM and BFM previously having a maximum sinking velocity of 10 and $4.25\ m\ d^{-1}$, respectively. The higher sinking velocities agree with data from phytoplankton aggregates from the PAP site in the Atlantic Ocean, where the majority of particles measured sank at velocities greater than $10\ m\ d^{-1}$ (slowest sinking speed $\approx 3\ m\ d^{-1}$ for a $\approx 1.75\ mm$ size particle ⁴⁷. Faecal pellet sinking rates from mesozooplankton sampled from the Western Channel Observatory in the English channel have also been measured to sink between $(50 - 160)\ m\ d^{-1}$ ^{48,49}.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Table 8 Summary of groups contributing to new CMEMS POC products for each model.

Model	Region	Groups contributing to 'living' POM	No. and type of detrital POM groups
ERSEM	NW European Shelf	4 phytoplankton + 2 zooplankton	3; small, medium and large
BFM	Mediterranean	4 phytoplankton + 4 zooplankton	2; small and large
ERGOM	Baltic	3 phytoplankton	1; non-specific sizes
ECOSMO	Arctic	4 phytoplankton + 2 zooplankton	1; non-specific size

Remineralisation of particulate organic carbon

Literature values for remineralisation rates are often based on incubation experiments and measuring changes in oxygen from bacterial remineralisation, although other methods can be used. Turnover rates for fast sinking particles have been measured to be $(0.007 - 0.04) \text{ d}^{-1}$ ^{45-47,50,51}. For slow sinking particles, calculations of turnover rates are much rarer. Cavan et al., (2017) found a turnover rate of $(5 \pm 0.4) \text{ d}^{-1}$ while Hemsley et al., (2023) found a turnover rate of $(0.43 - 1.7) \text{ d}^{-1}$. Slow sinking particles are typically smaller than fast sinking but with a higher surface area to volume ratio which leads to higher remineralisation rates.

7.2.3 Implementation

The different models all have different model structures and therefore different groups contributing to both total POC and detrital POC. In addition, equations describing the sinking of POC differ between the models. A summary of model groups contributing to 'living' and detrital POC for each model is shown in Table 8.

Table 9 Summary of processes impacting POC in each model.

Model	Sources of detrital POC	Sinks of detrital POC	Representation of sinking
ERSEM	4 phytoplankton, 3 zooplankton	Bacterial consumption	Each size class of POM has specific sinking speed which is constant for POC, PON and POP
BFM	4 phytoplankton, 4 zooplankton, 1 bacteria	Bacterial consumption	Constant sinking speed for each detrital POC
ERGOM	3 phytoplankton	Implicit remineralisation	Variable sinking speed for POM fractions
ECOSMO	4 phytoplankton + 2 zooplankton	Implicit remineralisation	Variable sinking speed as a function of weight averaged mass and prescribed sinking speed of the source terms to detritus

The representation of remineralisation of organic matter also differs between marine biogeochemical models with some having an explicit model of bacteria (ERSEM; BFM) that consume organic matter and convert it to inorganic carbon through respiration, whilst others implement an implicit approach defining a remineralisation rate (ERGOM; ECOSMO). A summary of whether explicit or implicit remineralisation is used in each model can be found in Table 9.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Table 10 Changes to ERSEM parameterisation for POC. Numbers in brackets represent original values in ERSEM

	Small	Medium	Large
Size (μm)	5	20	100
Sinking Speed (m d^{-1})	1 (1)	10 (5)	50 (10)
Bacterial Uptake Rate (d^{-1})	0.14 (0.01)	0.03 (0.0025)	0.007 (0.001)

ERSEM

Changes to POC sinking rates and remineralisation rates are implemented through changes in parameters in the fabm.yaml file rather than the model code. The ERSEM code does not include a direct remineralisation rate for POC but rather has a parameter for the availability of POC to bacteria in units of per day. This is not a direct comparison to the remineralisation rate measured experimentally as not all bacterial uptake of carbon will be converted to carbon dioxide or oxygen with some used for growth. Hence the numbers reported in the literature represent minimum values for the availability of POC to bacteria. Table 10 shows the proposed changes in parameters in ERSEM, highlighting the higher sinking speeds for the larger particles and up to an order of magnitude faster remineralisation rates for smaller particles.

To incorporate higher sinking speeds without numerical instabilities, a new numerical integration scheme for sinking particles was required within NEMO. The new scheme is a semi-lagrangian approach, which has recently been implemented in NEMO. This historically has been a barrier to implementing more realistic sinking rates within some of the biogeochemical models.

Table 11 BFM parameterisation of POC. Numbers in brackets represent original values in BFM.

	Small	Large
Size (μm)	<10	>10
Sinking speed (m d^{-1})	7 (4.25)	15 (N.D.)
Bacterial Uptake Rate (d^{-1})	0.012 (0.1)	0.03 (N.D.)
Fraction production by small plankton (-)	1 (N.D.)	0.0 (N.D.)
Fraction production by large plankton (-)	0.5 (N.D.)	0.5 (N.D.)

BFM

The number of detrital POC groups was increased from one to two, representing small, slow sinking particles; and large, fast sinking particles. Detrital POC is produced by phytoplankton; and zooplankton mortality and excretion (faecal pellets). Production of large and small particles scales with the plankton size class, with a parameter controlling how mortality and excretion fluxes are split between small and large POC. In the BFM, POC remineralisation is mediated by bacteria. A rate parameter quantifies the availability of each POC group to bacteria. Table 11 shows the parameterisation of POC sinking speeds and availability to bacteria in the new BFM code. These processes were implemented in both the fabm (bfmforfabm) and non-fabm (ogstm-bfm) versions of the BFM code.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

ECOSMO

ECOSMO includes a simple detritus model component and does not have an explicit bacteria state variable. Detritus is remineralized implicitly at a fixed rate (d^{-1}) and is also consumed during grazing by zooplankton. ECOSMO detritus has a variable sinking speed and at every time-step, a specific sinking speed is calculated based on the previous sinking speed and the prescribed sinking speeds of the individual sources of detritus. The slowest sinking detrital matter originates from flagellates ($0.5 m d^{-1}$) and the fastest originates from mesozooplankton ($10 m d^{-1}$). Based on weight averaging, the contribution of each source times its mass is added to the existing detritus concentration times the existing sinking speed, which yields the new sinking speed for that time step. This approach ensures that with the use of a single detrital component, seasonally and spatially varying sinking speeds are achieved. ECOSMO does not have a POM specific development in NECCON, but the inclusion of diel vertical migration of mesozooplankton results in changes in the POM concentration.

ERGOM

The ERGOM code used here is based on the implementation described by Thomas Neuman et al. ⁵². For this case study we linked the ERGOM code via FABM with the GOTM 1D water column model. The changes in parameterization were implemented through the fabm.yaml namelist file.

Table 12 ERGOM parameterisation of POC for BMPJ1.

POM	POC	POP/PON
Sinking speed ($m d^{-1}$)	9.0 (2.204)	0.1/0.1
Recycling Rate (d^{-1})	0.003	0.002
Formation Rate (d^{-1})	0.2 (0.01)	0.01

The parameterisation of POM fractions is detailed in Table 12. ERGOM includes a single pool for particulate organic matter (POM), consisting of particulate organic carbon (POC), particulate organic nitrogen (PON), and particulate organic phosphorus (POP). POC and PON/POP have different sinking velocities. The sinking velocities of POC varies with the location. POP and PON remain predominantly suspended in the water column, allowing them to represent small or less dense particles. The key sources of POC in the system are the production of DOC by the three functional phytoplankton types, which subsequently contributes to POC through aggregation and microbial processes. The dominant sink of POC is sedimentation as POC settles through the water column. During the sinking and sedimentation processes, the flux of POM is altered by bacterial processes implicitly simulated as remineralization, denitrification, sulphate reduction and respiration. These processes contribute to the breakdown of particulate organic matter, releasing nutrients and affecting the carbon cycle.

7.2.4 Testing

Results are shown for ERSEM, BFM, ERGOM and ECOSMO models. All results are based on 1D simulations. The ECOSMO results are distinct in the sense that they also combine the impact of DVM.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 16 Comparison of new parameters for POC sinking and remineralisation in the baseline and new versions of ERSEM for Total POC, Living POC and detrital POC at 10 m depth at station L4 in the Western English Channel. All observational data is for total POC.

ERSEM

The new parameters have been tested in a 1D setup at L4 in the Western English Channel. Results are compared with POC data sampled at a depth of 10 m. A baseline simulation was undertaken using the original ERSEM parameters. This was compared with a new simulation using the new parameters. For both the baseline and new models, three simulations were carried out: one investigating changes in sinking parameters, one investigating changes in remineralisation parameters and one looking at changes to both combined. The results indicate that the living component of POC contributes most to total POC. For this station, changing the sinking rates of detrital POC had a minimal impact on POC concentrations at 10 m depth. Changing the quantity of

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 17 BFM, comparison of observed (BGC-Argo backscattering) and simulated detrital POC in five BGC-Argo driven model setups (ARGO ids, 690XXXX) in the baseline (1xDet) and new (2xDet) versions of BFM. Error measures are normalised by the standard deviation of observations, with the bias (nbias) and mean absolute error (name) shown. The axes origin represents a perfect fit. In all model setups there is an improvement of either nmae or nbias, or both.

POC available to bacteria (remineralsation run) increases the living POC in summer through increased mineralisation of nutrients while the detrital POC decreases.

BFM

The new model formulation was tested in 1D setups that tracked the trajectories of selected BGC-Argo floats in the Mediterranean. The FABM BFM code was used, coupled with the 1D water column model GOTM. BGC-Argo float data provided estimates of particulate carbon (from backscattering) to evaluate model performance. BGC-Argo nitrate, salinity and temperature data were used as model forcings. Initial conditions were extracted from Copernicus reanalysis data for the Mediterranean Sea⁵³. Surface forcings (wind, pressure, rain, air temperature) were taken from ERA5 atmospheric reanalysis⁵⁴. Results show a good agreement between observed and simulated vertical profiles of both small and large POC (Figure 17). This includes the surface layers, where the POC signal is dominated by the living component, and at depth, where the signal is dominated by sinking detritus.

ECOSMO

Including diel vertical migration of mesozooplankton has direct consequences on the detritus concentration in multiple ways such that detritus is both a source, a mortality and sloppy-feeding byproduct for mesozooplankton, and a mortality byproduct for phytoplankton. For this reason, the positioning of mesozooplankton in the water column, the changes in grazing pressure (see phytoplankton concentration in Figure 18) due to DVM results in both vertical and temporal changes in detritus concentration further affecting the timing and magnitude of carbon export.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 18 2-year 1D GOTM-FABM-ECOSMO simulation Hovmöller diagram at a fixed-point location in the Norwegian Sea (66N -2E). Simulated detritus concentrations are depicted where DVM is not active (top plots), active (middle plots) and their difference (bottom plots; top - middle).

ERGOM

The testing of the modified parametrization is conducted at station BMPJ1, located in the Gotland Deep (57°19,20' N, 20°03.00' E). In Figure 19 a multi-year simulation of total POC is compared to observation data. The model most accurately represents POC concentrations during May, July, and August. However, during the non-growing season the model overestimates POC concentration in this configuration compared to observations. Due to modification to the sinking speed, recycling rate and formation rate (Table 12) the seasonal dynamics of POC concentration in the surface has improved. Both simulations capture seasonal variability, but the updated parametrization (Figure 19b) concerning POC have a stronger impact as the reduced phytoplankton exudation.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 19 Climatological comparison of model simulated surface total POC concentrations in the baseline simulation (blue line) and new simulation (red line). Solid lines represent the mean, shaded areas standard deviation. Observational data shows the mean and standard deviation. All statistical data presented here are based on the period from 2012 to 2022 at station BMPJ1. Top: POC concentrations resulting from reduced phytoplankton exudation. Bottom: Changes in POC concentrations due to modifications in sinking speed, recycling rate, and formation rate including reduced exudation.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

8 Dissolved Organic Matter

8.1 Introduction

Dissolved Organic Matter (DOM) is dissolved matter originating from living matter that operationally is not retained by filtration. The ocean contains approximately 7 giga tonnes of dissolved organic carbon (DOC) making it one of the largest bio-reactive pools of carbon in the ocean and over 200 times greater than carbon contained by marine biota. Oceanic DOC is a similar size to the atmospheric carbon pool⁵⁵. DOC is a critical component of the microbial loop where bacteria convert DOC to CO₂, and the microbial carbon pump⁵⁶, which turns labile DOC into refractory DOC which can be sequestered within the oceans interior.

Dissolved organic matter can be produced *in situ* from phytoplankton, zooplankton and bacteria and can also be of terrestrial origin. It is further modified through bacterial utilisation and photochemistry. Dissolved organic carbon is often separated into different fractions based on decomposition timescales into labile, semi-labile, semi-refractory and refractory pools. These fractions are produced and remineralised by a variety of processes that operate at different rates. Commonly the refractory pool is not included within models as its turnover time is on the order of 100-1000s of years. However, it contributes to >50 % to DOC in the Atlantic Ocean⁵⁷ and so needs to be added on to model outputs when comparing with observations. Typically, the refractory pool is considered to be around 44 µM.

In NECCTON, we have enabled the delivery of model DOC products for three domains: the Arctic, the NW European Shelf and the Baltic Sea. In addition, the improvement of DOC indirectly supports bio-optical modelling through Coloured DOM (CDOM), which is an important bio-optical component. The underlying models were improved by revisiting phytoplankton DOC exudations rates. In this section, we describe the parameterisation of DOC exudation and summarise published rates. The new process was tested using PyFABM and various 1 and 3D model configurations.

8.2 Dissolved Organic Carbon Exudation

8.2.1 Background

Dissolved organic carbon exudation is the release of dissolved organic carbon from phytoplankton. The release of DOC by phytoplankton is a critical component of the carbon cycle, and can represent in excess of 35 % of the net primary production flux in nutrient limited conditions⁵⁷⁻⁶⁰.

8.2.2 Theory

The precise mechanisms for the phytoplankton exudation of DOC is debated and magnitude and importance difficult to elucidate⁵⁷. Two conceptual models have been proposed for the release of DOC: the overflow model, and the passive diffusion model. In the overflow model DOC release is related to decoupling between photosynthesis limited by light availability, and cell growth limited by nutrient availability. Thus, the release of DOC is a strategy that can dissipate energy while still undergoing photosynthesis when the cell is nutrient limited. Exudation correlates with the

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

photosynthetic rate and is carbon rich. In the passive diffusion model, the release of DOC is related to the concentration gradient of DOM and is correlated with the biomass of the cell. It is greater for smaller than larger plankton due to their higher surface area to volume ratio.

A common metric for calculating phytoplankton exudation is the percent extracellular release (*PER*) which normalises DOC release to particulate and dissolved net primary production (*NPP*) :

$$PER = \frac{ER}{NPP}$$

(36)

Where *ER* is phytoplankton extracellular release and *NPP* is net primary production, which includes both the particulate and dissolved components. *PER* is reported to be (5 – 35)% of *NPP*, with lower *PER* in productive regions and higher *PER* in oligotrophic regions⁵⁷. As such *PER* is expected to be higher when phytoplankton are undergoing nutrient stress

8.2.3 Implementation

Since DOC has a variety of sources there is not a standalone module for DOC. Ordinary differential equations for DOC are instead embedded into individual modules providing source and sinks of DOC. The modules changed as part of NECCTON for each model are provided in Table 13 and described in the sections below for each individual model. Table 13 provides details on the sources and sinks of DOM from each individual model.

Table 13 Models, DOM pool names, and their sources and sinks

Model	Number and names of DOM pools	Sources of DOM	Sinks of DOM
ERSEM	3; labile, semi-labile, semi-refractory	4 phytoplankton, 3 zooplankton, bacteria	Bacterial uptake
ECOSMO	1; labile	4 phytoplankton, 2 zooplankton, 1 detritus	Remineralization
ERGOM	1; labile	3 phytoplankton	Flocculation, mineralization

ERSEM

In the current version of *ERSEM*, and as described in Butenschön et al⁶¹, the release of DOC by phytoplankton is comprised of two components. These are activity dependant excretion (Q_{act}) and phytoplankton exudation regulated by nutrient stress (Q_{nut}):

$$Q_{act} = S_{GPP} \cdot q_{excr}$$

(37)

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

$$Q_{nut} = S_{GPP} \cdot (1 - l_{(NP)}) \cdot (1 - q_{excr})$$

(38)

Here, S_{GPP} is Gross Primary Production (GPP), q_{excr} is the excreted fraction of S_{GPP} , and $l_{(NP)}$ a nutrient limitation term calculate using Droop kinetics ⁶², and minimum of N and P limitations calculated using internal cell nitrogen:carbon and phosphorus:carbon quotas.

Figure 20 Percent extracellular release as function of internal cellular C:N ratio for the baseline and new simulations, calculated using PyFABM. This represents the response of picophytoplankton in constant light conditions, with a Redfieldian internal C:P ratio.

The total flux of DOC released by phytoplankton Q_{tot} is then:

$$Q_{tot} = Q_{act} + Q_{nut}$$

(39)

In theory, 100 % of GPP could be released as DOC by phytoplankton when in extreme nutrient limiting conditions, which does not agree with observational data. Therefore, a limit has been introduced which reduces the amount of DOC released by phytoplankton under nutrient stress:

$$Q_{nut} = S_{GPP} \cdot (1 - l_{(NP)}) \cdot q_{exu}$$

(40)

This includes the condition:

$$q_{excr} \leq 1 - q_{exu}$$

(41)

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

where q_{exu} is the fraction of GPP released due to nutrient limiting conditions.

Figure 21 Climatology of model predicted surface DOC concentrations in the baseline simulation (black line) and new simulation (red line) with the developments above incorporated. Solid lines represent the mean, shaded areas +/- 1 standard deviation. Observational data shows the mean and standard deviation. Observational data for BATS is from 1993-2016, while at Station L4 is from 2011-2014.

A key feature of ERSEM is that nutrient limitation affects more the assimilation of newly fixed carbon into cellular biomass than photosynthesis itself and thus GPP is not impacted by nutrients⁶¹. However, limiting the amount of DOC exudated can result in very high cellular nutrient:carbon ratios. Therefore, a factor has been added to GPP which limits GPP when the cell quota approaches the minimum P:C or N:C values. On the Northwest European Shelf, this should make a minimal impact but may become more important in oligotrophic conditions.

Following estimates of *PER*, the q_{excr} has been set to 0.05 and represents the background release of DOC independent of nutrient conditions, and q_{exu} is 0.3. No published data on these values for different phytoplankton groups was found, so the same values have been applied to all phytoplankton functional types.

ECOSMO

ECOSMO has a basic representation of DOC in which a fraction detritus production (mortality, grazing) is allocated to the DOC pool. The sink term for DOC is remineralization with a fixed rate (d^{-1}). In NECCTON, we incorporate DOC release by phytoplankton. Both background release (excretion) and exudation due to nutrient-limitation is included in the new formulation. The DOC release in ECOSMO did not replace an existing phytoplankton sink term but was added as an additional sink term. The same q_{exu} and q_{excr} values for ERSEM were used in ECOSMO.

ERGOM

The ERGOM version used here is based on the implementation described by⁵². The changes in parameterization were implemented using the *fabm.yaml* namelist.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 22 Comparison between total model DOC (including additional refractory DOC of 44 μM) for the baseline simulation and the new model for August 2000. Runs performed using NEMO-ERSEM and a Northwest European Shelf configuration.

The extracellular DOC produced by phytoplankton (small cells, large cells, and cyanobacteria) contributes to the formation of Transparent Exopolymer Polymers (TEP). The model includes a parameterisation of flocculation of DOM, which is modeled using a rate-based approach. Flocculation results in the formation of POC. Nutrient limitation triggers labile DOM production. In case of N and P limitation the fraction of DOC production increases. The dissolved organic matter is in general carbon-enriched, represented by a flexible element ratio, with the lowest compositional limit being the Redfield ratio.

8.2.4 Testing

ERSEM

The impact of the new parameterisation of exudation of DOC has been tested using PyFABM (Figure 20). The results clearly show the reduction in DOC release by phytoplankton in the new formulation.

The developments were further tested at two contrasting 1D stations and compared against a reference pre-NECCTON simulation: one station in the oligotrophic Sargasso Sea (BATS), the other in the eutrophic Western English Channel (L4). Both stations have observational DOC data to validate the model with. An additional 44 μM DOC was added to the total DOC predicted by the model to represent the non-modelled refractory fraction of DOC.

Figure 21 demonstrates the change in extracellular release as a function of nutrient stress at the oligotrophic BATS station. In the new formulation *PER* has reduced to around (0.1 - 0.35) %, corresponding with the observational data. High *PER* only occurs when very low nutrients are present. In contrast, in the baseline simulation *PER* is much greater than observational values for all concentrations of nitrate.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 23 Improvement in model predicted DOC vs observations for NEMO-ERSEM for the baseline simulation and new code. As the model was only run the 1 year the comparisons are matched for day of year rather than specific dates. Only observational data with salinities > 25 were used to avoid data in estuarine systems, where the influence of terrestrial DOC is highest.

Testing the new formulation in a 1D water column model using GOTM-ERSEM indicates that the developments have greatly improved predictions for DOC at BATS, with the baseline model overestimating DOC concentrations (Figure 21). At L4, model predicted DOC concentrations are lower and the seasonality of DOC concentrations reduced in the new simulations compared to the baseline. There is an improvement in summer predictions for DOC while winter predictions are maybe too low. However, L4 is a coastal 1D station and we do not include the influence of terrestrial DOC in our model runs. Terrestrial DOC is expected to have a bigger influence in the winter due to high river discharges⁶³, and that could explain the discrepancy seen in the new model's predictions for DOC. In addition, 1D models do not include advection which further could explain the discrepancy in results

The new code has also been tested for 1 year (2000) in 3D (NEMO-ERSEM) using a model configuration for the Northwest European Shelf and compared to the baseline simulation (Figure 22). The simulation has been compared against observations obtained from global open ocean DOC⁶⁴, coastal DOC⁶⁵ and supplemented with data from the North Sea⁶⁶ (Figure 23) Only a small number of observations for DOC are available for the NW European Shelf and these mostly occur in August in the North Sea. Results indicate that NEMO-ERSEM in the baseline simulation is greatly over-predicting DOC concentrations in summer compared to observational data. The new developments reduce summer DOC within NEMO-ERSEM and greatly improve model predictions with observational data.

ECOSMO

Simulations shows changes in both DOC and total phytoplankton concentrations (Figure 24). As expected, additional DOC source term through excretion and exudation results in increased DOC

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 24 2-year 1D GOTM-FABM-ECOSMO simulation Hovmöller diagram at a fixed-point location in the Norwegian Sea (66N -2E). Simulated DOC concentrations are depicted where DOC release is not active (top plots), active (middle plots) and their difference (bottom plots; top - middle).

concentration. The effect on phytoplankton is not straightforward as there are seasonally opposing changes. The beginning of the spring bloom shows a decrease in phytoplankton biomass followed by an immediate increase, with a minor decrease in phytoplankton biomass throughout the summer. A general (minor) decrease is expected because DOC release was included in ECOSMO as a separate sink term in addition to loss due to mortality and grazing. While there is a decrease in phytoplankton biomass in the earlier stages of the spring bloom, probably due to DOC being an extra sink term, the immediate increase right after the decrease in biomass is mostly related to increased recycling of organic matter, since DOC remineralization is much faster compared to detritus, and DOC does not sink, so will continue to recycle at the source location.

ERGOM

The ERGOM version used here is based on the implementation described by Thomas Neumann et al.⁵². The changes in parameterization were implemented using the fabm.yaml namelist.

The refractory part of DOM is not featured in ERGOM, therefore the results include a bias when compared with observations. For the Baltic Proper, near-surface DOC concentration of (305 – 335) mmol C m^{-3} ^{52,67}, have been observed during the non-growing season.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 25 Climatologies of predicted surface total DOC concentrations in the baseline simulation (blue line) and new simulation (red line) using ERGOM. Solid lines represent the mean, shaded areas standard deviation. Observational data show the mean and standard deviation. All data presented here are based on the period from 2012 to 2022 at station BMPJ1. Top: DOC concentrations resulting from reduced phytoplankton exudation. Bottom: Changes in DOC concentrations due to modifications in POC sinking speed, recycling rate, and formation rate, including reduced exudation.

The testing of the modified parametrization is conducted at station BMPJ1, located in the Gotland Deep (57°19,20' N, 20°03.00' E). In Figure 25, a multi-year simulation of total DOC is shown with observation data. The seasonal cycle of labile organic matter is overestimated during the growing season, starting with the onset of the spring bloom. To more accurately represent the DOC

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

concentration (Figure 25, top-panel), the exudation of phytoplankton has been reduced by 10 %. Additionally, modifications to the sinking speed, recycling rate, and formation rate (Table 12) resulted in significant improvements in representing doc dynamics in the growing season.

9 Bio-optical modelling

9.1 Introduction

Light is key to ecosystems, photosynthesis, the carbon cycle and primary production. Moreover, the components of light (photons) are messenger particles that transport information. In recent years, several bio-optical models have been developed to better understand light propagation through the water column. These models can be validated with data from satellite sensors, or optical sensors in general. Data provided by state-of-the-art satellite sensors can be fully exploited with adequate bio-optical models.

Propagation of light within the water column is modulated by the interaction with optical constituents such as water itself, plankton, coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM), detritus and sediment. In the following, we describe the suite of bio-optical models developed in NECCTON and their implementation in the BAMHBI, BFM, ERGOM and ERSEM models.

Each biogeochemical model targets a different region (see Table 14), and depending on the characteristics of the biogeochemical model used, the bio-optical model considers a different number of components, e.g. a different number of phytoplankton functional types (PFTs), CDOM constituents and non-living organic particulate carbon pools (organic detritus). All models consider at least one of the three components: i) phytoplankton, ii) CDOM, and iii) organic detritus.

The bio-optical models are based on two main elements. The first element is a simplified version of a radiative transfer model that resolves light propagation and its spectral discretization, which is influenced by absorption and scattering. All NECCTON radiative transfer models are based on the three-stream approach with further simplifications depending on the region under consideration. All the models have the same spectral resolution (25 nm) in the visible spectrum (400 - 700) nm. The second element is based on the relationships between the concentrations of the optical components and their mass-specific absorption and scattering.

This relationship is formulated as a set of linear polynomials of the model state (diagnostic) variables such as phytoplankton chlorophyll and carbon concentration, CDOM concentration and detritus concentration. The coefficients of the polynomials are derived from experimental data corresponding to the respective regions.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Table 14 Optical constituents considered in the model implementations for the different sites.

REGION	MODEL	PHY	CDOM	DETRITUS
Baltic Sea	ERGOM	3 PFTs, Nitrate	1CDOM	1 Detritus
Black Sea	BAMHBI	3 PFTs	Forced	1 Detritus
Mediterranean Sea	BFM	4 PFTs Carbon Chlorophyll	3 CDOM, Carbon [labile/semi labile/ semi refractory]	2 Detritus, Carbon
North West Shelf	ERSEM	4 PFTs	3 CDOM [as Med]	3 Detritus

The bio-optical model is necessary to simulate multispectral remote sensing reflectance (R_{rs}), which is a new NECCON product. It can also be used to compute the seabed irradiance product (WP6) and to study the dynamics of pollutants (e.g. mercury photoreduction, WP8). In addition, all processes covered in NECCON T.5.2.1, T.5.2.2 and T.5.2.3 are related to light propagation and are therefore indirectly linked to bio-optical modelling activity. In this section, we describe developments to the models that support the delivery of a Reflectance product. Testing is performed in 1D and 3D.

9.2 Reflectance

9.2.1 Background

Reflectance (RRS) is the ratio of the electromagnetic flux reflected by a surface to the total electromagnetic flux incident on the surface. Water reflectance, as a function of the wavelength of electromagnetic radiation, provides useful information about the different types of suspended and dissolved components of biotic and abiotic matter in the ocean. RRS is used to identify various spectral features through the analysis of their inherent optical properties (i.e., absorption and backscattering). For example, RRS is used to derive chlorophyll using empirical algorithms.

9.2.2 Theory

The incoming spectral irradiance at the surface of the ocean was obtained from the OASIM model linked to the atmospheric model of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) ^{68,69}. The input data included two downward components just below the sea surface: direct [$Ed(\lambda, 0-)$] and diffuse [$Es(\lambda, 0-)$] (both in $W m^{-2}$ defined over 33 wavebands). The irradiance through the depth of the water column (z) was described by three state variables (all in $W m^{-2}$): downward direct [$Ed(\lambda, z)$] and diffuse [$Es(\lambda, z)$] components and an upward diffuse component [$Eu(\lambda, z)$]. The vertically resolved three-stream propagation can be expressed as a system of differential equations ⁷⁰⁻⁷² and solved analytically by adopting different published approximations ⁷³⁻⁷⁵.

The ratio between the upward component and the sum of the downward components ($Eu/(Ed+Es)$) is used to derive reflectance. With additional corrections to normalize over the solid angle ⁷⁶, and considering the water atmosphere interface ⁷⁷, it is possible to obtain RRS that is directly comparable with satellite measurements ⁷⁴.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Table 15 Processes directly affected by the novel bio-optical model.

REGION	IRRADIANCE/Rrs	PHOTOSYNTHESYS	CDOM PHOTOBLEACHING
Baltic Sea	YES	NO	YES [PAR based]
Black Sea	YES	YES	NO
Mediterranean Sea	YES	YES [PFTs specific PUR]	YES [PAR based]
North West Shelf	YES	YES	YES [PAR based]

9.2.3 Implementation

All implementations are based on the same conceptual model of light propagation (3-stream model), but the code base follows different implementations. The OASIM atmospheric model is the same for BFM, ERGOM and ERSEM and it available based as a FABM module (see Table 2). The same atmospheric code is also available as a separate code base developed within the BIOPTIMOD repository. Moreover, BFM and ERGOM use the same in-water model, which is also publicly available as a FABM model. The BAMHBI implementation is based on the same method for the in-water model. However, the atmospheric model is a regional MAR configuration for the Black Sea, extended with the ecRad radiative scheme (Hogan and Bozzo, 2018).

The mass-specific absorption and scattering coefficients are usually normalized to chlorophyll and carbon, respectively. Therefore, a conversion factor must be applied if the internal currency of the model is different, as in the case of ERGOM, which is based on nitrogen. This process is facilitated by the modular structure of FABM. The bio-optical model can be linked to various processes. It can be used as a diagnostic module to calculate reflectance without a feedback with the biogeochemistry. It can be used to calculate the scalar irradiance, which is then integrated into the visible range and converted into photosynthetically available radiation (PAR); in this case, all phytoplankters experience the same PAR. Finally, the bio-optical model can be used to calculate the photosynthetically utilized radiation (PUR), which depends on the specific optical traits of the organisms ^{73,78}. In addition, the bio-optical model can be used to calculate CDOM photobleaching ^{73,79}. The specific configuration of each regional model is summarized in Table 15.

The input parameters for the bio-optical model are the spectral coefficients of absorption, scattering and back-scattering of sea water, phytoplankton and detritus absorption, scattering and back-scattering coefficients and CDOM absorption coefficients. Seawater optical parameters are well established and available from the literature: absorption is derived from Pope and Fry ⁸⁰, and scattering and back scattering from Smith and Baker ⁸¹.

NAP and detrital optical parameters are derived from an empirical power law relation that exhibits exponentially decreasing curves with increasing wavelength (Gallegos et al., 2011), where different classes of particles can be considered, from biotic (small or large biological particles) to abiotic particles (small, large minerals).

CDOM has exponentially decreasing absorption curves ⁸², with parameters available for different regions. The different origin of allochthonous CDOM (e.g. ligneous compounds from river discharge) or autochthonous CDOM (e.g. produced in situ by plankton) could be correlated to different spectral

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

absorption shapes. Phytoplankton is characterized by typical mass-normalized absorption curves that depend on the specific pigments of the phytoplankton functional type under consideration. Many taxa show a characteristic bimodal absorption curve with one peak in the blue and one in the red wavelength range. Specific studies to aggregate available information in key plankton functional types have been conducted for a global ocean implementation ⁷³, and for the Mediterranean Sea ⁷⁸.

All the developments used in the modelling tests performed in this section have been made available in the [NECCTON dedicated repository](#); in particular, ERGOM-NECCTON for the Baltic Sea, bamhbi-rt for the Black Sea, BFMFORFABM for the Mediterranean Sea, ERSEM-NECCTON (cdom branch) and fabm-spectral (rrs branch) for the North West Shelf.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

9.2.4 Testing

In this section, we describe the result of 1D and 3D tests that have been performed with the different biogeochemical models.

ERGOM

Modification to the ERGOM routines include the addition of FABM calls to enable dynamic tracer interactions with the spectral module. CDOM is implemented as a single pool tracer in the ERGOM model⁸³. The CDOM tracer is divided into three fractions (labile, refractory, and semi-refractory), to account for the spectral component. Functional phytoplankton groups are specified as diatoms, flagellates, and cyanobacteria, with biomasses converted from nitrogen to carbon units. For the radiation propagation in the atmosphere hourly ERA5 data on water vapor and cloud liquid water content are considered.

The testing of a 1D ERGOM-GOTM-SPECTRAL configuration is conducted at station BMPJ1, located in Gotland Deep (57°19,20' N, 20°03.00' E). In Figure 26, the simulated monthly reflectance (red) and observed satellite reflectance (blue) from CMEMS (Product ID: OCEANCOLOUR_BAL_BGC_L3_MY_009_133), are compared for the period 2020-2022. Olci satellite data are provided as a multiyear, high-resolution product with a spatial resolution of 300 meters across 21 spectral bands.

The remote sense reflectance exhibits a large spread, due to limited data availability caused by cloud cover in winter. The highest reflectance is observed around 560 nm, corresponding to the yellow

Figure 26 ERGOM reflectance (red) and satellite reflectance (blue) at the Baltic Sea station BMPJ1. Dots show monthly mean values from 2020-2022 and error bars show the spread in data.

Project	NECCOTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 27 Remote-sensed reflectance in 2018 in the Western gyre site. Average monthly data is represented by circle for BAMHBI (in red) and remote-sensed data (in green). Bars show the spread in data for each month.

range of the visible spectrum, where Gelbstoff (CDOM) dominates. With the onset of the Spring bloom in March, the consistency between the model and satellite data improves significantly. Both datasets show a reduced spread, reflecting increased data quality and consistent conditions. During Summer and late Summer, the modelled reflectance slightly overestimates the satellite measurements. This overestimation may be caused by the late Summer bloom of cyanobacteria, which might be in this configuration overestimated by the ERGOM model.

BAMHBI

A three-stream radiative transfer model was added to the 3D BAMHBI framework, vertically resolving in-water irradiance streams in 33 wavebands. The spectral resolution in the visible range is 25 nm. The optically active components considered are pure water, phytoplankton, non-algal particles and CDOM. Optical properties for phytoplankton are adapted from published studies^{73,78}, to match the three PFTs solved in BAMHBI. We use POC concentration (simulated in BAMHBI) to derive optical properties for non-algal particles. As CDOM is not simulated in the model, its contribution is forced. Profiles of CDOM absorption were derived from BGC-ARGO data in the central region of the Black Sea to derive reference absorption profiles that include seasonal variability. As such, we expect the model to perform better in the deep basin where the optical properties were more adequately tuned. We have also implemented an option allowing the activation of a feedback from the radiative transfer model to the physics (NEMO) and the biogeochemistry (BAMHBI), in the computation of temperature and primary production respectively.

Primarily, the calibration of optical parameters was performed using BGC-ARGO data for irradiance streams and remote-sensed data. BGC-ARGO data were taken from ARGO floats with IDs 6901866, 6903240 and 7900591 between 2016 and 2018. We used remote-sensed reflectance data from the CMEMS ocean colour L3 multi-satellite product (Product ID: OCEANCOLOUR_BLK_BGC_L3_MY) for the years 2016 and 2017. We tested the model by running 3D simulations in the entire Black Sea.

On the western coast of the basin, AERONET-OC stations Galata and Gloria⁸⁴, provide measurements of water-leaving irradiance, but do not provide biological or chemical data. Nonetheless, we use the Galata site (43.05N, 28.19E) as a coastal validation site. This study site is influenced by river discharges from the northwest of the basin, and the largest biological activity occurs in Winter and early Spring. We expect the model to show more limitations in this region, as it was mostly calibrated using data from the deep basin, thus accounting little for coastal dynamics.

In the absence of a long-term validation site in the deep basin, we use an arbitrary location to perform a comparison with remote-sensed data in the central Black Sea. Here, we consider a point

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 28 Remote-sensed reflectance in 2018 at the Galata station. Average monthly data is represented by circle for BAMHBI (in red) and remote-sensed data (in green). Bars show the spread in data for each month.

in the Western gyre of the basin (42.80N, 30.89E). A large bloom is expected in Spring, followed by a smaller coccolithophore bloom in early summer.

The seasonal patterns for 2018 at the western gyre study site are presented in Figure 27. The model can simulate reflectance outside of bloom events consistently with remote-sensed data. We notice the signature of blooms in the observations, but the reflectance increase is not as important in the model as it is in the data. Simulated reflectance remains within the data range and in agreement with remote-sensed data.

Monthly results at the Galata station are presented in Figure 28. We identify in the satellite signal a Winter bloom (December/January) and a larger bloom in March. Both are picked up by the model but mixed within a wide bloom that includes February, thus overestimating reflectance then. Lower reflectances are consistent in Summer and slightly too high in Autumn, with the winter bloom starting a bit earlier than in observations. Results are again mostly in agreement with satellite data.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 29 Monthly means of Remote sensing for the months of January, February, March and April, reflectance on the two selected sites. OC_MULTI_BO and OC_MULTI_AA are the data for BOUSSOLE and Acqua Alta sites respectively, BFM_1D_BO and BFM_1D_AA are the corresponding model outputs. Satellite data are the reflectance multisensor dataset (cmems_obs-oc_med_bgc-reflectance_my_l3-multi-1km_P1D) in the L3 daily Satellite Observations product (OCEANCOLOUR_MED_BGC_L3_MY_009_143) for 2017.

BFM

FABM-BFM model has been extended with a three-stream spectral radiative model resolving the propagation of in-water irradiance through the water column discretized in 33 wavelengths with 13 of them in the visible. Phytoplankton optical parameters have been collected based on absorption and scattering spectra measured on phytoplankton cultures and statistically aggregated for the four PFTS currently defined in the BFM⁷⁹. Mass specific absorption and scattering are chlorophyll and carbon based respectively. Beside phytoplankton, absorption and scattering parameterizations depend on non-living organic particulate carbon fraction⁸⁵. We also included SPM concentrations from the transparency multi-sensor dataset (cmems_obs-oc_atl_bgc-transp_my_l3-multi-1km_P1D) in the North Atlantic L3 daily Satellite Observations product (OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_BGC_L3_MY_009_113) because we found it fundamental to reconstructing $RRS(\lambda)$ variability in coastal areas. We upgraded the FABM-BFM prototype to improve DOC and CDOM dynamics, with three reactivities: labile, semi-labile and semi-refractory. In particular, we implemented a novel formulation where DOC that leaked constantly from phytoplankton cells is considered to have a chromophoric fraction proportional to cell pigmentation, whereas DOC exuded

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 30 As figure 29 for the months of May, June, July, August.

under intra-cellular nutrient shortage is considered to be non-absorbing, and therefore it is not partitioned into CDOM ⁷⁹.

We deployed the GOTM-FABM-BFM prototype in two contrasting sites, an open-ocean ecosystem in the Ligurian Sea, the BOUSSOLE observatory, and a coastal site in the Northern Adriatic Sea, the Acqua Alta Oceanographic Tower (AAOT).

The BOUSSOLE site is located in the Ligurian Sea (7°54'E, 43°22'N) at about 32 nautical miles from the French coast (water depth is 2440 m). Here an autonomous fixed buoy has been deployed since 2003, sampling bio-optical parameters every 15 min, and monthly oceanographic cruises have been conducted since 2001 for discrete bio-optical sampling. This site shows a marked seasonality of the physical forcing, switching from deep mixed layers in Winter to a prevailing stratification in Summer. Oligotrophic conditions prevail during the Summer period. The productive early spring phytoplankton bloom period usually occurs from February to April.

The Acqua Alta Oceanographic Tower (AAOT) is located about 8 miles off the coast of Venice (12°30'E, 45°19'N), where the water depth is approximately 16 m. The AAOT contains radiometric sensors and infrastructure for real-time data transfer, and it is also a fixed point for periodic acquisition of water column samples and analysis of biological and chemical parameters. This site is subject to complex hydrodynamic processes including anti-clockwise circulation and the influence of

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 31 As figure 29 for the months of September, October, November, December.

winds that affect circulation patterns and water exchange between the open sea and coastal area. Several major rivers, including the Po River, flow into the Northern Adriatic, contributing freshwater, sediment, and nutrients to the sea. Although these relatively nutrient-rich waters promote the growth of phytoplankton, being one of the most eutrophic areas of the entire North Adriatic Sea, there is an important presence of material of terrestrial origin.

For the two sites, we performed a sensitivity analysis to explore which optical and biogeochemical parameters influence most the $RRS(\lambda)$ bands simulated as well as the concentrations of Chlorophyll-a and phytoplankton carbon in superficial waters. The most influential parameters across outputs were targeted for calibration purposes and optimized using as observational data the reflectance multisensor dataset (cmems_obs-oc_med_bgc-reflectance_my_l3-multi-1km_P1D) in the L3 daily Satellite Observations product (Product ID: OCEANCOLOUR_MED_BGC_L3_MY_009_143) for 2014 to 2016. To evaluate model improvement, we compared the same CMEMS Ocean colour data product with the GOTM-FABM-BFM prototype for the year 2017 disaggregated per month, Figure 29-31.

The two sites express very different spectral signatures, the BOUSSOLE site showing clear blue water $RRS(\lambda)$ shapes whilst AAOT show a clear peak in the green. This feature is typical of higher absorption in the blue region and higher particle scattering due to the strong influence of riverine forcings and resuspensions. The model can capture the contrasting behaviour of the two sites, in particular for the BOUSSOLE site. The signature of absorption by phytoplankton ($RRS(400-500) < 0.05 \text{ st}^{-1}$) during the winter period is clearly visible in satellite data and correctly reproduced by the

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

Figure 32 Monthly climatologies of satellite OC-CCI data (black line) and ERSEM-modelled sea surface reflectance (red and green lines) for a range of wavelengths at station L4 in the Western English Channel. The model was run in 1D using GOTM. The red and green lines represent different absorption and scattering properties for small vs large inorganic SPM, with only one type represented in the 1D model.

model. In the AAOT site, the model overestimates $RRS(\lambda)$ in the green band around 500 nm during May and June, and underestimates it during the months of November and December. Overall, the model results are coherent with observed satellite data.

ERSEM

ERSEM is coupled to FABM-spectral, a 2-stream hyperspectral model. As there is no direct upwelling term in fabm-spectral (i.e., the third stream), an analytical solution has been applied to the model to calculate reflectance. FABM-spectral is based on the OASIM model⁷² and the analytical solution originates from the OASIM equations, using the assumption that all the optical interactions happen within the mixed layer. This assumption is justified based on the observation that surface visibility on the Northwest European Shelf is typically between (5 -15) m⁶⁹, while the mixed layer is most of the time deeper than this.

FABM-spectral has previously been coupled to ERSEM and run on the Northwest European Shelf⁶⁹. However, this model run also included an external product to represent the absorption by detritus and coloured DOM (CDOM). In NECCON, this variable is modelled explicitly.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

On the Northwest European Shelf it is important to include inorganic SPM in the model as this will impact the absorption and scattering of light, especially near to the coast. Following the developments for SPM, two groups of SPM have been included – one for mud and one for sand. Absorption and scattering properties have been assigned for both groups, following Gellagos et al.⁸⁵, for small and large inorganic matter corresponding to mud and sand respectively. The values are independent of individual sinking speeds of different sands and muds within the SPM module in ERSEM.

Following published examples of modelling CDOM^{79,86,87}, CDOM has been added to ERSEM. Three new state variables were added to the model, corresponding to labile, semi-labile and semi-refractory CDOM. Labile and semi-labile CDOM is produced by phytoplankton and zooplankton. In standard runs, CDOM is assumed to be a constant fraction of the DOC produced by phytoplankton and zooplankton. However, there is also an option to follow Álvarez et al., (2023), where DOC produced under nutrient stress is colourless and therefore does not add to the CDOM fraction, while the fraction of CDOM released by activity excretion is dynamic based on the chlorophyll:carbon ratio of the phytoplankton functional group. A new module has been added to ERSEM for photobleaching/photodegradation which includes two different options. In the first option, photobleaching saturates once light is more than $60 \mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. CDOM is then converted to the colourless fraction of DOC^{73,79}. In the second option, the quantum yield and quantum absorption by CDOM of the available spectral irradiance in the water column is used⁷². In this case a fraction of the degradation product goes into to more labile fraction of colourless DOC while the rest is converted to DIC⁶³.

Following testing against observational data for CDOM absorption at station L4 in the Western English Channel, the absorption coefficient for CDOM was set to $0.015 \text{ m}^2 \text{ mg C}^{-1}$ ^{73,79}. In addition, it was decided to follow the photodegradation formulation from Greg and Rousseaux⁷².

We have simulated the surface spectral reflectance at Station L4 for the 2012-2017 6 year-period. After 2 years of spin-up, we have used 2014-2017 years to estimate a daily climatology of the reflectance at the wavelengths: 412nm, 443nm, 490nm, 510nm, 560nm, and 665nm. This has been compared with a daily observed climatology extracted from the OC-CCI v6.0 1998-2020 time-series. The results are presented in Figure 32. The size of inorganic SPM particles has a marked impact on the simulated reflectance, with the satellite data lying between simulations performed with small and large inorganic particles. The exception is the months of May and June, when the simulated reflectance drops off significantly, while the satellite data only falls to lower values in July. In the model, this period corresponds to a time when SPM concentrations fall due to reduced rainfall and runoff, and the timing of the Spring Bloom, when the concentration of CDOM and detritus rises; with the model struggling to simulate the combined impact of these on reflectance. It is expected changes to DOC exudation will also influence these results.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

10 Conclusions

In this report, we have provided a description of the additions and improvements made to the suite of marine biogeochemical models being used in NECCTON, and their relationship to the new pelagic lower trophic level products that are being delivered. In total, the work enables the delivery of five new products, and involved developments to all seven of the biogeochemical models that currently support the delivery of the Copernicus Marine Service. Included were a description of new processes designed to improve the way mesozooplankton are represented in models. Mesozooplankton are a key link between the lower and higher trophic levels of the marine food web, and thus an important determinant of fish production.

The work in NECCTON has involved adding a new description of Diel Vertical Migration for mesozooplankton, and a parameterisation of light dependent mortality – two factors which are known to be a major source of uncertainty in models. Also included was a description of work focussed on resolving feedbacks between micronekton and the lower trophic levels of the marine food web, with the aim of better capturing seasonal changes in micronekton biomass. Micronekton are organisms which measure (2 – 20) cm in size and are an important source of food for higher trophic level organisms. To our knowledge, very few studies have focused on micronekton seasonality, and none have explored it using models. By addressing this gap, we position ourselves as pioneers in advancing the understanding of micronekton seasonal dynamics.

A new model of Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) was also described. SPM is a collective term for the inorganic (e.g., mineral) and organic (e.g., detritus; see next section) particulates suspended in the water column. It is an indicator of sediment transport, water clarity and quality; and has important implications for pelagic and benthic productivity and erosion. It can also act as a vector for the transfer of pollutants and contaminants. We described a new SPM module that has been developed for the fine-scale, unstructured hydrodynamic model SHYFEM-MPI. The model was tested in 3D using a local, high-resolution model domain for the Tyrrhenian Sea. This module was then rewritten for FABM and incorporated into the ERSEM model, where it will support the delivery of a new SPM product for the Northwest European Shelf domain. A separate model of SPM was developed for BAMHBI, where it was run with NEMO to study the transport of organic SPM in the Black Sea.

The results of improving parameterisations relating to the production and processing of particulate and dissolved organic matter were also described. The work has enabled the delivery of a product representing particulate organic carbon for four domains: the Arctic, the Mediterranean Sea, the NW European Shelf and the Baltic Sea. We have improved the underlying models by revisiting how sinking and remineralisation rates are modelled using recent data from the published literature. For dissolved organic carbon, the underlying models were improved by revisiting phytoplankton DOC exudations rates. In test simulations, the developments are shown to better reproduce new observations for both particulate and dissolved organic carbon.

Finally, the report included the description of a new bio-optical model which supports the delivery of a new product for multispectral remote sensing reflectance, which can be directly compared with

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

satellite reflectance data. The accurate simulation of light penetration and reflectance is of fundamental importance in marine ecosystem models, as light is the primary source of energy input to the marine ecosystem. The new bio-optical model can be used to compute seabed irradiance and to study the dynamics of pollutants (e.g. mercury photoreduction).

The document is designed to be read in conjunction with NECCTON D5.1, where the new pelagic lower trophic level products are defined. The document also provides context to the suite of multi-decadal hindcasts which are being run within NECCTON, and which include the new processes described herein.

11 References

1. Archibald, K. M., Siegel, D. A. & Doney, S. C. Modeling the Impact of Zooplankton Diel Vertical Migration on the Carbon Export Flux of the Biological Pump. *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycles* **33**, 181–199 (2019).
2. Brierley, A. S. Diel vertical migration. *Curr. Biol.* **24**, R1074–R1076 (2014).
3. Steinberg, D. K. & Landry, M. R. Zooplankton and the Ocean Carbon Cycle. *Annu. Rev. Mar. Sci.* **9**, 413–444 (2017).
4. Henson, S. A. *et al.* Uncertain response of ocean biological carbon export in a changing world. *Nat. Geosci.* **15**, 248–254 (2022).
5. Rohr, T., Richardson, A. J., Lenton, A., Chamberlain, M. A. & Shadwick, E. H. Zooplankton grazing is the largest source of uncertainty for marine carbon cycling in CMIP6 models. *Commun. Earth Environ.* **4**, 1–22 (2023).
6. Aksnes, D. L. *et al.* Light penetration structures the deep acoustic scattering layers in the global ocean. *Sci. Adv.* **3**, e1602468 (2017).
7. Xie, J., Raj, R. P., Bertino, L., Samuelsen, A. & Wakamatsu, T. Evaluation of Arctic Ocean surface salinities from the Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity (SMOS) mission against a regional reanalysis and in situ data. *Ocean Sci.* **15**, 1191–1206 (2019).
8. Hersbach, H. *et al.* The ERA5 global reanalysis. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* **146**, 1999–2049 (2020).

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

9. McEvoy, A. J. *et al.* The Western Channel Observatory: a century of physical, chemical and biological data compiled from pelagic and benthic habitats in the western English Channel. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **15**, 5701–5737 (2023).
10. Aksnes, D. L. Evidence for visual constraints in large marine fish stocks. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **52**, 198–203 (2007).
11. Neumann, T. & Kremp, C. A model study with light-dependent mortality rates of copepod stages. *J. Mar. Syst.* **56**, 416–434 (2005).
12. Gupta, S., Lonsdale, D. J. & Wang, D.-P. The recruitment patterns of an estuarine copepod: a biological-physical model. (1994).
13. Pinti, J. *et al.* Model estimates of metazoans' contributions to the biological carbon pump. *Biogeosciences* **20**, 997–1009 (2023).
14. Ariza, A., Garijo, J. C., Landeira, J. M., Bordes, F. & Hernández-León, S. Migrant biomass and respiratory carbon flux by zooplankton and micronekton in the subtropical northeast Atlantic Ocean (Canary Islands). *Prog. Oceanogr.* **134**, 330–342 (2015).
15. Bianchi, D., Stock, C., Galbraith, E. D. & Sarmiento, J. L. Diel vertical migration: Ecological controls and impacts on the biological pump in a one-dimensional ocean model. *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycles* **27**, 478–491 (2013).
16. Saba, G. K. *et al.* Toward a better understanding of fish-based contribution to ocean carbon flux. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **66**, 1639–1664 (2021).
17. Steinberg, D. K. *et al.* Zooplankton vertical migration and the active transport of dissolved organic and inorganic carbon in the Sargasso Sea. *Deep Sea Res. Part Oceanogr. Res. Pap.* **47**, 137–158 (2000).
18. Aumont, O., Maury, O., Lefort, S. & Bopp, L. Evaluating the Potential Impacts of the Diurnal Vertical Migration by Marine Organisms on Marine Biogeochemistry. *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycles* **32**, 1622–1643 (2018).

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

19. Petrik, C. M., Stock, C. A., Andersen, K. H., van Denderen, P. D. & Watson, J. R. Bottom-up drivers of global patterns of demersal, forage, and pelagic fishes. *Prog. Oceanogr.* **176**, (2019).
20. Conchon, A. Modélisation du zooplancton et du micronecton marins. *Modélisation Zooplanct. Micronecton Mar.* (2016).
21. Lehodey, P. *et al.* Optimization of a micronekton model with acoustic data. *ICES J. Mar. Sci.* **72**, 1399–1412 (2015).
22. Lehodey, P., Murtugudde, R. & Senina, I. Bridging the gap from ocean models to population dynamics of large marine predators: A model of mid-trophic functional groups. *Prog. Oceanogr.* **84**, 69–84 (2010).
23. Aumont, O., Ethé, C., Tagliabue, A., Bopp, L. & Gehlen, M. PISCES-v2: an ocean biogeochemical model for carbon and ecosystem studies. *Geosci. Model Dev.* **8**, 2465–2513 (2015).
24. Albernhe, S. *et al.* Global characterization of modelled micronekton in biophysically defined provinces. *Prog. Oceanogr.* **229**, 103370 (2024).
25. Gloeckler, K. *et al.* Stable isotope analysis of micronekton around Hawaii reveals suspended particles are an important nutritional source in the lower mesopelagic and upper bathypelagic zones. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **63**, 1168–1180 (2018).
26. Pearre, S. Eat and run? The hunger/satiation hypothesis in vertical migration: history, evidence and consequences. *Biol. Rev. Camb. Philos. Soc.* **78**, 1–79 (2003).
27. Choy, C. A., Popp, B. N., Hannides, C. C. S. & Drazen, J. C. Trophic structure and food resources of epipelagic and mesopelagic fishes in the North Pacific Subtropical Gyre ecosystem inferred from nitrogen isotopic compositions. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **60**, 1156–1171 (2015).
28. Hannides, C. C. S., Popp, B. N., Choy, C. A. & Drazen, J. C. Midwater zooplankton and suspended particle dynamics in the North Pacific Subtropical Gyre: A stable isotope perspective. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **58**, 1931–1946 (2013).

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

29. Wentworth, C. K. A Scale of Grade and Class Terms for Clastic Sediments. *J. Geol.* **30**, 377–392 (1922).
30. Soulsby, R. L. *Dynamics of Marine Sands*. (Thomas Telford, London., 1997).
31. Sharqawy, M. H., Lienhard, J. H. & Zubair, S. M. Thermophysical properties of seawater: a review of existing correlations and data. *Desalination Water Treat.* **16**, 354–380 (2010).
32. Whitehouse, R. J. S., Soulsby, R. L., Roberts, W. & Mitchener, H. *Dynamics of Estuarine Muds*. (Thomas Telford, London., 2000).
33. Van Rijn, L. C. *Principles of Sediment Transport in Rivers, Estuaries and Coastal Seas*. (Aqua Publications, 1993).
34. Soulsby, R. & Whitehouse, R. Threshold of Sediment Motion in Coastal Environments. in (1997).
35. Rijn, V. & C, L. Sediment Transport, Part I: Bed Load Transport. *J. Hydraul. Eng.* **110**, 1431–1456 (1984).
36. Van Rijn, L. C. Unified View of Sediment Transport by Currents and Waves. I: Initiation of Motion, Bed Roughness, and Bed-Load Transport. *J. Hydraul. Eng.* **133**, 649–667 (2007).
37. van Rijn, L. C. *et al.* Critical Bed-Shear Stress of Mud–Sand Mixtures. *J. Hydraul. Eng.* **151**, 04024050 (2025).
38. Ariathurai, R. & Arulanandan, K. Erosion Rates of Cohesive Soils. *J. Hydraul. Div.* **104**, 279–283 (1978).
39. Warner, J. C., Sherwood, C. R., Signell, R. P., Harris, C. K. & Arango, H. G. Development of a three-dimensional, regional, coupled wave, current, and sediment-transport model. *Comput. Geosci.* **34**, 1284–1306 (2008).
40. Micaletto, G. *et al.* Parallel implementation of the SHYFEM (System of Hydrodynamic Finite Element Modules) model. *Geosci. Model Dev.* **15**, 6025–6046 (2022).

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

41. Escudier, R. *et al.* Mediterranean Sea Physical Reanalysis (CMEMS MED-Currents) (Version 1) [Data set]. E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information (CMEMS).
https://doi.org/10.25423/CMCC/MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004_E3R1 (2020).
42. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S). Sea surface temperature daily data from 1981 to present derived from satellite observations. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS). <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.cf608234> (2019).
43. Boyd, P. W., Claustre, H., Levy, M., Siegel, D. A. & Weber, T. Multi-faceted particle pumps drive carbon sequestration in the ocean. *Nature* **568**, 327–335 (2019).
44. Cael, B. B., Cavan, E. L. & Britten, G. L. Reconciling the Size-Dependence of Marine Particle Sinking Speed. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **48**, e2020GL091771 (2021).
45. Cavan, E. L., Trimmer, M., Shelley, F. & Sanders, R. Remineralization of particulate organic carbon in an ocean oxygen minimum zone. *Nat. Commun.* **8**, 14847 (2017).
46. Hemsley, V. *et al.* Suspended particles are hotspots of microbial remineralization in the ocean’s twilight zone. *Deep Sea Res. Part II Top. Stud. Oceanogr.* **212**, 105339 (2023).
47. Belcher, A. *et al.* Depth-resolved particle-associated microbial respiration in the northeast Atlantic. *Biogeosciences* **13**, 4927–4943 (2016).
48. Cole, M. *et al.* Microplastics Alter the Properties and Sinking Rates of Zooplankton Faecal Pellets. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **50**, 3239–3246 (2016).
49. Coppock, R. L. *et al.* Microplastics alter feeding selectivity and faecal density in the copepod, *Calanus helgolandicus*. *Sci. Total Environ.* **687**, 780–789 (2019).
50. Collins, J. R. *et al.* The multiple fates of sinking particles in the North Atlantic Ocean. *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycles* **29**, 1471–1494 (2015).
51. McDonnell, A. M. P., Boyd, P. W. & Buesseler, K. O. Effects of sinking velocities and microbial respiration rates on the attenuation of particulate carbon fluxes through the mesopelagic zone. *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycles* **29**, 175–193 (2015).

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

52. Neumann, T., Radtke, H., Cahill, B., Schmidt, M. & Rehder, G. Non-Redfieldian carbon model for the Baltic Sea (ERGOM version 1.2) – implementation and budget estimates. *Geosci. Model Dev.* **15**, 8473–8540 (2022).
53. Feudale, L. *et al.* Mediterranean Sea Biogeochemical Analysis and Forecast (CMEMS MED-Biogeochemistry, MedBFM4 system). Copernicus Marine Service
https://doi.org/10.25423/cmcc/medsea_analysisforecast_bgc_006_014_medbfm4 (2023).
54. Hersbach, H. *et al.* ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS) <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47> (2023).
55. Friedlingstein, P. *et al.* Global Carbon Budget 2023. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **15**, 5301–5369 (2023).
56. Jiao, N. & Zheng, Q. The Microbial Carbon Pump: from Genes to Ecosystems. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **77**, 7439–7444 (2011).
57. Carlson, C. A. & Hansell, D. A. Chapter 3 - DOM Sources, Sinks, Reactivity, and Budgets. in *Biogeochemistry of Marine Dissolved Organic Matter (Second Edition)* (eds. Hansell, D. A. & Carlson, C. A.) 65–126 (Academic Press, Boston, 2015). doi:10.1016/B978-0-12-405940-5.00003-0.
58. Baines, S. B. & Pace, M. L. The production of dissolved organic matter by phytoplankton and its importance to bacteria: Patterns across marine and freshwater systems. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **36**, 1078–1090 (1991).
59. Marañón, E., Cermeño, P. & Pérez, V. Continuity in the photosynthetic production of dissolved organic carbon from eutrophic to oligotrophic waters. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* **299**, 7–17 (2005).
60. Teira, E., José Pazó, M., Serret, P. & Fernández, E. Dissolved organic carbon production by microbial populations in the Atlantic Ocean. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **46**, 1370–1377 (2001).
61. Butenschön, M. *et al.* ERSEM 15.06: a generic model for marine biogeochemistry and the ecosystem dynamics of the lower trophic levels. *Geosci. Model Dev.* **9**, 1293–1339 (2016).

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

62. Droop, M. R. Nutrient Status Of Algal Cells In Continuous Culture. *J. Mar. Biol. Assoc. U. K.* **54**, 825–855 (1974).
63. Powley, H. R. *et al.* Modelling terrigenous DOC across the north west European Shelf: Fate of riverine input and impact on air-sea CO₂ fluxes. *Sci. Total Environ.* **912**, 168938 (2024).
64. Hansell, D. *et al.* Compilation of dissolved organic matter (DOM) data obtained from global ocean observations from 1994 to 2021. Version 2 (NCEI Accession 0227166). NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information <https://doi.org/10.25921/s4f4-ye35>. (2021).
65. Lønborg, C. *et al.* A global database of dissolved organic matter (DOM) concentration measurements in coastal waters (CoastDOM v1). *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **16**, 1107–1119 (2024).
66. Painter, S. C. *et al.* Terrestrial dissolved organic matter distribution in the North Sea. *Sci. Total Environ.* **630**, 630–647 (2018).
67. Maciejewska, A. & Pempkowiak, J. DOC and POC in the water column of the southern Baltic. Part I. Evaluation of factors influencing sources, distribution and concentration dynamics of organic matter. *Oceanologia* **56**, 523–548 (2014).
68. Lazzari, P. *et al.* Assessment of the spectral downward irradiance at the surface of the Mediterranean Sea using the radiative Ocean-Atmosphere Spectral Irradiance Model (OASIM). *Ocean Sci.* **17**, 675–697 (2021).
69. Skakala, J., Bruggeman, J., Brewin, B., Ford, D. & Ciavatta, S. Improved Representation of Underwater Light Field and Its Impact on Ecosystem Dynamics: A Study in the North Sea. *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans* **125**, (2020).
70. Aas, E. Two-stream irradiance model for deep waters. *Appl. Opt.* **26**, 2095–2101 (1987).
71. Ackleson, S. G., Balch, W. M. & Holligan, P. M. Response of water-leaving radiance to particulate calcite and chlorophyll a concentrations: A model for Gulf of Maine coccolithophore blooms. *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans* **99**, 7483–7499 (1994).

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

72. Gregg, W. W. & Rousseaux, C. S. Directional and Spectral Irradiance in Ocean Models: Effects on Simulated Global Phytoplankton, Nutrients, and Primary Production. *Front. Mar. Sci.* **3**, (2016).
73. Dutkiewicz, S. *et al.* Capturing optically important constituents and properties in a marine biogeochemical and ecosystem model. *Biogeosciences* **12**, 4447–4481 (2015).
74. Lazzari, P., Gharbi Dit Kacem, M., Álvarez, E., Chernov, I. & Vellucci, V. Determination of biogeochemical properties in sea waters using the inversion of the three-stream irradiance model. *Sci. Rep.* **14**, 22347 (2024).
75. Salama, Mhd. S. & Verhoef, W. Two-stream remote sensing model for water quality mapping: 2SeaColor. *Remote Sens. Environ.* **157**, 111–122 (2015).
76. Aas, E. & Højerslev, N. K. Analysis of underwater radiance observations: Apparent optical properties and analytic functions describing the angular radiance distribution. *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans* **104**, 8015–8024 (1999).
77. Lee, Z., Carder, K. L. & Arnone, R. A. Deriving inherent optical properties from water color: a multiband quasi-analytical algorithm for optically deep waters. *Appl. Opt.* **41**, 5755–5772 (2002).
78. Álvarez, E., Lazzari, P. & Cossarini, G. Phytoplankton diversity emerging from chromatic adaptation and competition for light. *Prog. Oceanogr.* **204**, 102789 (2022).
79. Álvarez, E. *et al.* Chromophoric dissolved organic matter dynamics revealed through the optimization of an optical–biogeochemical model in the northwestern Mediterranean Sea. *Biogeosciences* **20**, 4591–4624 (2023).
80. Pope, R. M. & Fry, E. S. Absorption spectrum (380–700 nm) of pure water. II. Integrating cavity measurements. *Appl. Opt.* **36**, 8710–8723 (1997).
81. Smith, R. C. & Baker, K. S. Optical properties of the clearest natural waters (200–800 nm). *Appl. Opt.* **20**, 177–184 (1981).
82. Bricaud, A., Morel, A. & Prieur, L. Absorption by dissolved organic matter of the sea (yellow substance) in the UV and visible domains. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **26**, 43–53 (1981).

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	2023-2026
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	26 February 2025	Version	1.0

83. Neumann, T. *et al.* Optical model for the Baltic Sea with an explicit CDOM state variable: a case study with Model ERGOM (version 1.2). *Geosci. Model Dev.* **14**, 5049–5062 (2021).
84. Zibordi, G. *et al.* Advances in the Ocean Color Component of the Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET-OC). (2021) doi:10.1175/JTECH-D-20-0085.1.
85. Gallegos, C. L., Werdell, P. J. & McClain, C. R. Long-term changes in light scattering in Chesapeake Bay inferred from Secchi depth, light attenuation, and remote sensing measurements. *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans* **116**, (2011).
86. Bissett, W. P., Carder, K. L., Walsh, J. J. & Dieterle, D. A. Carbon cycling in the upper waters of the Sargasso Sea: II. Numerical simulation of apparent and inherent optical properties. *Deep Sea Res. Part Oceanogr. Res. Pap.* **46**, 271–317 (1999).
87. Xiu, P. & Chai, F. Connections between physical, optical and biogeochemical processes in the Pacific Ocean. *Prog. Oceanogr.* **122**, 30–53 (2014).